

ELEVATE: Enabling and Leveraging Climate Action Towards Net-Zero Emissions

Grant agreement no. 101056873

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01

D4.3 – International trade measures and carbon club

Work Package: D4.3: International trade measures and carbon club

Due date of deliverable: 31st January 2025

Actual submission date: 27th February 2025

Start date of project: 1st May 2023

Duration: 20 months

The lead beneficiary for this deliverable: E3M

Contributors: Ioannis Charalampidis, Dimitris Fragkiadakis, Zoi Vrontisi, Paola Rocchi, Edoardo Campo Lobat, Alice Di Bella, Valentina Bosetti, Régis Rathmann and Roberto Schaeffer

Internal reviewers: Isabela Schmidt Tagomori

**Funded by
the European Union**

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon Europe Programme		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	√

1. Changes with respect to the description of work

This deliverable focuses on the socio-economic and trade implications of existing and potential carbon border adjustment mechanisms. The assessment is based on large scale economic models. The analysis does not explicitly take into account the impact of targets set by International Civil Aviation Organization as originally stated as more focus has been put on the assessment of CBAM implications.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is public and will be available at ELEVATE's website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report includes the findings of three individual impact assessments on the economic implications of carbon adjustment measures, performed with the use of three well-established computable general equilibrium (CGE) models (GEM-E3-FIT, FIDELIO, PAEG). No common scenario framework is assumed; instead, alternative specifications of a future world where EU's CBAM plays a central role are examined and each study focuses on a different group of countries. The PAEG CGE model examines the impacts of EU CBAM and national carbon pricing schemes on the EU27 and the Brazilian economy, the FIDELIO model performs similar scenario assessment for EU27, China and India, while the GEM-E3 model examines the impacts of the CBAM adoption by different group of countries on the 10 greatest global economic forces (EU27, Turkey, China, India, Indonesia, Japan, South Korea, Australia, USA and Canada) . All models find minimal impacts of the EU CBAM both at the EU27 level and at the global state in terms of GDP and of emission reductions, while the implementation of stringer climate policies by non-EU countries yields higher impacts for both variables.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

See report below.

Version log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
1	25/02/2025	E3MODELLING	Final version for internal review
2	27/02/2025	PBL	Final version for submission

Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	1
2. Assessing the economic and trade implications of a gradual adoption of CBAM by major global economies	2
2.1. Introduction and literature review	2
2.2. Trade status and global production in selected energy intensive industries	5
2.3. Methodology	11
2.4. Results	18
2.5. Conclusions	34
2.6. References	34
3. Environmental and economic impacts of EU CBAM and SBCE on the competitiveness of the main Brazilian commodities on the international market.....	35
3.1. Introduction.....	35
3.2. Methodology.....	36
3.3. Results	38
3.4. Conclusions	42
3.5. References	42
4. Expanding carbon pricing boundaries and the EU CBAM: insights into China and India...	44
4.1. Introduction.....	44
4.2. Literature review	49
4.3. Methodology.....	50
4.4. Results	56
4.5. Conclusions	63
4.6. References	65
Appendix A.....	72
Appendix B.....	73
Appendix C.....	74
Appendix D.....	76

1. Introduction

This deliverable aims to assess the impacts of international trade measures, such as carbon border adjustments (CBAs) on international trade and macroeconomic performance and to also examine the influence of climate clubs to the reduction of global emissions. In this deliverable, the analysis from three modelling teams is included in the form of individual assessments. Each of the below sections describes a model-specific analysis.

In section 2, E3 -Modelling, with the use of the global computable general equilibrium model (CGE), GEM-E3-FIT, assesses the economic impacts of alternative CBAM country clubs. The first scenario (EUCBAM) assumes that CBAM is adopted only by the EU27 countries, while the second scenario (CBAMG1) assumes that another group of countries (Group1) consisting of USA, UK and Australia also implements carbon tariffs, and finally in the third scenario (CBAMG2) on top of EU27 and Group 1 countries China, India and Canada also implement CBAs. The list of products covered by carbon tariffs includes iron and steel, aluminum, fertilizers, cement, electricity and hydrogen. The simulation results reveal relatively small changes both in GDP and in global trade volume, topping at -0.11% and -0.15% in 2050 respectively, in the CBAMG2 scenario. In terms of emissions, the introduction of carbon tariffs achieves mild global greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reductions of approximately -0.6% in 2050. This implies that the incentives provided by the imposition of carbon tariffs to exporters to adopt more emission efficient production processes are rather weak. In overall, changes are driven primarily by the iron and steel industry and to a lesser extent by aluminum. In terms of bilateral trade, the most impacted countries are China and Japan which due to their relatively higher emission intensity record export losses to countries that adopt CBAs. Lost market shares are partly overtaken by domestic industries and by exporters with higher emission efficiency. Side-effects include the reduction in exports of energy goods, such as oil and gas, an effect which is more evident in Indonesia and in China.

In section 3, UFRJ/COPPETEC, use the PAEG CGE model to assess the impacts of EU CBAM and of carbon taxation in Brazil. Two scenarios are drawn against a baseline case: the first scenario examines the implication of EU CBAM to the Brazilian economy, while the second assumes that Brazil introduces also a carbon taxation scheme. The analysis finds mild GDP impacts under the EUCBAM scenario, with EU GDP increasing between 0.10% and 0.20% (up to 2050), while the Brazilian economy is projected to record losses of up to approximately -0.4% in 2050. In terms of emissions, at the global level, the introduction of CBAM in the EU achieves mild emission reductions of -0.2% approximately. The implementation of carbon taxation has greater impacts both on the economy and emissions in Brazil leading to a decrease in GDP of more than 3.5% and of approximately 11% in emissions.

In section 4, CMCC applies the global general equilibrium model FIDELIO to estimate the impacts of the EU CBAM in the economy of China and of India. Seven distinct scenarios are modelled which include a combination of EUCBAM implementation and the adoption of national carbon pricing policies in India and in China. The scenario formulation allows for the individual assessment of each of the above measures as well as their combination identifying the most important drivers behind macroeconomic changes and changes in GHG emissions. GDP impacts under the EUCBAM scenario are found to be generally small in magnitude (<0.5%). Russia records the highest GDP losses among countries examined, while EU27 GDP is found to be positively affected in 2030 driven mainly by higher production in high energy intensive industries which is offset by 2040 by lower production in other sectors. Small negative impacts are projected for China and India throughout the projection period. In terms of international trade the introduction of CBAM in EU27 implies a shift from high emitting exporters such as China and India to less emitting such as USA and an increase of intra-EU trade. The implementation of carbon pricing in India and China, leads to higher variations in GDP and emissions compared to the first scenario. China's emission can decrease as much as 26% under a scenario with Chinese + Indian ETS + EU CBAM, while in the same case India's emission can reduce by 22.5%. The corresponding GDP impacts for those countries are found to be equal to approximately -2% in 2040.

2. Assessing the economic and trade implications of a gradual adoption of CBAM by major global economies

2.1. Introduction and literature review

The European Commission has announced in 2023 the adoption of a carbon adjustment mechanism (EU CBAM Regulation 2023/956), as an indispensable part of its ambitious climate policy which would lead to a 55% reduction in emissions by 2030 and to climate neutrality by 2050. The implementation of the CBAM is twofold: on the one hand to protect vulnerable European industries which are prone to competitiveness losses and carbon leakage, on the other hand to incentivize exporters to the EU to adopt more environmentally friendly production processes. As we are still far from reaching a consensus on global action and effort sharing to combat climate change, it is highly likely that, in a world of unilateral climate action, more countries will follow the example of the EU by adopting similar mechanisms.

The assessment of CBA's implications on the economy and on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions has been an important topic of the CGE impact assessment studies for the past twenty years. Early studies, around the 2010's (Kuik and Hofkes 2010, Böhringer, Carbone and Rutherford 2012a, 2012b, Fischer and Fox 2012, Caron 2012) focused on the evaluation of alternative policy options with respect to their effectiveness in

limiting carbon leakage and protecting energy intensive industries from competitiveness losses, especially under the assumption of unilateral climate actions. Fisher and Fox (2012) examine the effectiveness of import tax, export rebate, full border assessment and output-based rebates. They conclude that given their model specification and assumptions on global climate policies, carbon order adjustment is the most effective tool in alleviating the pressure of carbon tax in the domestic economy. Böhringer, Carbone and Rutherford 2012a in their overview, question the effectiveness of CBA on reducing carbon leakage, the associated cost savings and the degree to which energy intensive industries are protected with the aid of twelve modelling teams. In overall, they find that CBA's reduce leakage rate by approximately 4% on average compared to a non-CBA reference scenario, reduces production losses in energy intensive industries from 2.8% to 1% and leads to cost savings which implies lower GDP impacts.

The interest on CBAM impacts has been reignited with the adoption of the EU CBA. Most of these studies focus on quantifying country-specific impacts of the EU CBAM on trade flows, GDP and employment. On average, minimal impacts both on economic variables and in emissions are to be expected.

What can be drawn from previous impact assessment is a consensus that CBAs are an effective tool for reducing carbon leakage, there is a consensus among studies that the implementation of CBAM raises concerns regarding its contradiction to WTO rules, as well as real challenges regarding the consistent accounting of emissions. Furthermore, the taxation based on the carbon content can be further broadened to include also induced emissions besides direct emissions from fossil fuels combustion.

Table 1: List of studies assessing the impacts of CBA

Year	Authors	Model	Countries	GDP impacts
2024	Takeda S. and Arumura T.S.	CGE multi country	Japan	0.002% (Japan), -0.01% (EU27)
2024	Long Chu et al.	Single country CGE	Vietnam	-0.10%
2023	Clora et al.	GTAP-E-RD	EU	ranging from -0.04% to -0.07%
2022	IMPACT ASSESSMENT REPORT Accompanying the document Proposal for a regulation of the European	GEM-E3 JRC	EU27	ranging from -0.222% to -0.227%

	Parliament and of the Council establishing a carbon border adjustment mechanism			
2023	Gu et al.	GTAP CGE	China, India, Brazil, South Africa	EU27: -0.13%% compared to no tax scenario under CBAM, -0.18% with no CBAM and carbon tax. India and South Africa most sensitive to EU CBAM implementation
2022	Ramadani & Koo	GTAP CGE	Indonesia	-0.0250%
2021	Acar, S., Aşıcı, A.A. & Yeldan, A.	AGE model	Turkey	ranging from -2.7% to -3.6%

The growing interest in CBAM is now expanding beyond the EU, with major economies such as the United States, China, Canada, Australia and Japan beginning to explore similar measures.

The United States, for example, has been considering the possibility of implementing carbon pricing and border adjustment mechanisms, with bipartisan support emerging for policies that could mirror aspects of the EU's CBAM. China, which is the world's largest emitter of greenhouse gases, has also expressed its intentions to transition toward a greener economy, and it may eventually adopt a CBAM-like system to safeguard its own industries from competitive disadvantages in international markets. Japan, too, has been actively exploring ways to integrate carbon considerations into trade policy.

Canada, with its strong commitment to addressing climate change and carbon emissions, has been closely watching the EU's implementation of CBAM. The Canadian government has been advancing its own climate policies, including carbon pricing and clean technology investments, and is considering how a CBAM could complement its domestic efforts to reduce emissions. Canada, a major exporter of natural resources, particularly in the energy sector, could face challenges if countries with more stringent carbon standards impose CBAM-like measures. A Canadian CBAM could also align its trade relations with the EU and other like-minded nations, helping to ensure that its industries are not disadvantaged in global markets. Jebeli et al. (2025) examine from Canada's perspective alternative policy options to reduce carbon leakage and their impact on the economy. They find that CBAM is more effective compared to free allocation in reducing carbon leakage rates and leads to small changes in welfare (<1%).

Australia, similarly, has engaged in discussions around carbon pricing and climate action, though it has historically taken a more cautious approach to strict carbon regulations. Australia's major export industries, including coal, iron ore, and agricultural products, could face challenges from CBAM policies, as these sectors are highly carbon intensive. The Safeguard Mechanism¹, which describes the set of actions to reduce Australia's emissions in major emitting industrial facilities, is exploring measures to reduce carbon leakage among which is the introduction of CBAM².

These countries' potential adoption of CBAM could fundamentally reshape global trade dynamics and climate policy. As more countries implement similar mechanisms, international supply chains would be forced to adjust to a more fragmented regulatory environment, where carbon content would become a critical factor in the pricing and competitiveness of goods.

In this paper we conduct a model-based assessment of the EU CBAM but also consider potential the expansion of the border adjustment mechanisms in large economies, as described above. The analysis is performed with the large-scale hybrid CGE model, GEM-E3, and focuses on macroeconomic, trade and emission implications. The paper is structured with an introductory overview of global trade data for products under the EU CBAM, the description of our methodology, including the model definition and the scenario design, followed by the results and conclusions section.

2.2. Trade status and global production in selected energy intensive industries

Carbon tariffs can be applied to a variety of imported goods, but the main interest is on energy and carbon intensive industries, whose competitiveness depends highly on energy and carbon prices. In our assessment, we focus on the highly traded products covered by the EU-CBAM regulation, namely iron and steel, aluminum, fertilizers and cement. China is the larger exporter in most of these commodities, with shares that reach as much as 18% of global trade for iron and steel. In fertilizers, Canada holds also a significant share in global markets while in cement, middle east and north African countries rank in the first places among exporting countries, with Turkey ranking the largest exporter in the world.

¹ <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/climate-change/emissions-reporting/national-greenhouse-energy-reporting-scheme/safeguard-mechanism>

² <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/climate-change/emissions-reduction/review-carbon-leakage>

Table 2: Global export market shares by country and by CBAM sector (COMTRADE)

	Cement	Iron & Steel	Aluminium	Fertilizers
United Kingdom	0.48%	1.28%	1%	0.68%
Turkey	11.50%	2.23%	2.64%	0.76%
USA	1.68%	3.81%	5.12%	8.28%
Canada	4.78%	1.94%	6.90%	14.52%
China	2.43%	18.02%	13.18%	14.77%
India	0.38%	3.06%	4.05%	0.16%
Indonesia	0.38%	3.06%	4.05%	0.16%
South Korea	0.90%	6.01%	2.41%	0.65%
Japan	2.35%	6.51%	0.97%	0.18%
Australia	0.03%	0.16%	2.41%	0.34%

Trade patterns are important to identify the sensitivity of sectorial exports to potential CBA measures. Low differentiation with respect to destination markets, increases the sensitivity of the home country export performance in the case of unilateral BCA. With respect to bilateral trade in iron and steel (Table 3), the majority of Turkey's and UK's exports are driven to Europe (33% and 65% respectively). The EU27 also holds an important share of Indian exports (approximately 33%). Other significant interdependencies are those of Indonesia from China, as the latter is the destination for approximately 66% of total Indonesian iron & steel exports, Canada from the US (93%) and Brazil from USA and EU27 (59%).

In aluminum (Table 4), Turkey, India and China and the UK are the largest exporters to the EU in absolute terms. Exports to the EU account for 64% of total Turkish exports, 72.4% of United Kingdom's total exports and 14% of total Indian exports. Chinese exports are relatively evenly distributed among regions with Europe receiving 6% of aluminum produced in China, and USA, India and Japan approximately 5%.

In chemical fertilizers (Table 5), EU27 is again the main market of destination for Turkish and UK products. The second most important market for UK's products is Brazil where approximately 16% of total exports are headed to. While India is the main destination of Chinese and Indonesian fertilizers, accounting for approximately 17% and 15% of the respective country's total fertilizer exports. Finally, in cement trade (Table 6), relative geographical proximity explains largely the pattern of trade.

Table 3: Iron and Steel: Bilateral exports by country – COMTRADE data for 2023 in milion.\$

	Australia	Brazil	Canada	China	India	Indonesia	Japan	Rep. of Korea	Turkey	United Kingdom	USA	EU27	Total
Australia	0	0	19	6	17	25	1	4	3	7	247	99	774
Brazil	6	0	331	1368	68	22	361	227	160	130	7120	2113	15567
Canada	17	14	0	39	30	2	3	12	3	9	8906	153	9570
China	864	2579	958	0	3750	4005	1790	7117	3552	335	1778	5453	88656
India	150	196	227	564	0	402	196	464	565	393	1263	4946	15070
Indonesia	200	24	18	18342	1648	0	34	355	447	52	164	649	27561
Japan	184	270	213	3560	1389	2256	0	4394	598	138	2155	1942	32017
Rep. of Korea	347	289	624	2703	2533	976	3354	0	1654	285	3706	4124	29580
Turkey	63	48	281	5	22	2	45	13	0	295	378	3624	10992
United Kingdom	26	89	75	92	62	9	23	35	266	0	490	4086	6318
USA	95	217	7434	391	153	12	146	160	101	254	0	1330	18724
EU27	305	1351	1311	2188	1135	508	250	617	3615	5616	8473	0	169590

Table 4: Aluminum: Bilateral exports by country – COMTRADE data for 2023 in bn.\$

	Australia	Brazil	Canada	China	India	Indonesia	Japan	Rep. of Korea	Turkey	United Kingdom	USA	EU27	Total
Australia	0	2	17	62	40	104	802	1147	0	2	306	118	3502
Brazil	0	0	1	2	0	0	362	1	0	0	133	308	1184
Canada	0	1	0	11	4	0	0	1	1	8	9417	300	10039
China	647		657	0	986	518	979	1586	258	311	894	1143	19159
India	22	104	29	222	0	48	402	816	188	53	380	810	5884
Indonesia	43	0	14	228	16	0	10	11	59	9	114	28	695
Japan	5	6	4	553	11	39	0	98	1	5	176	130	1417
Rep. of Korea	108	4	9	862	158	78	208	0	124	1	538	305	3508
Turkey	0	2	61	6	1	0	0	0	0	174	275	2441	3832
United Kingdom	7	5	6	19	34	3	11	13	15	0	112	1056	1458
USA	22	55	2073	127	51	9	243	234	66	125	0	341	7441
EU27	60	205	223	319	146	25	169	168	647	2426	1598	0	46212

Table 5: Fertilizers: Bilateral exports by country – COMTRADE data for 2023 in bn.\$

	Australia	Brazil	Canada	China	India	Indonesia	Japan	Rep. of Korea	Turkey	United Kingdom	USA	EU27	Total
Australia	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	0	0	1	25	2	204
Brazil	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	181
Canada	5	391	0	390	277	243	1	1	0	1	2737	46	4509
China	351	486	6	0	1015	450	205	231	64	2	104	47	6006
India	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	5	77
Indonesia	25	8	5	0	41	0	2	7	0	1	0	0	280
Japan	1	0	1	8	1	1	0	14	0	0	20	12	115
Rep. of Korea	16	0	0	1	15	10	37	0	13	0	1	8	330
Turkey	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	58	195
United Kingdom	1	37	2	14	3	0	0	0	2	0	6	145	237
USA	221	814	998	102	178	5	170	111	14	10	0	121	3728
EU27	50	520	73	184	50	91	18	14	151	580	158	0	9847

Table 6: Cement: Bilateral exports by country – COMTRADE data for 2023 in bn.\$

	Australia	Brazil	Canada	China	India	Indonesia	Japan	Rep. of Korea	Turkey	United Kingdom	USA	EU27	Total
Australia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Brazil	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
Canada	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	441	1	444
China	25	1	1	0	5	1	10	9	1	1	95	8	578
India	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	271
Indonesia	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	129
Japan	63	0	0	2	5	0	0	26	0	0	1	5	359
Rep. of Korea	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	24	0	106
Turkey	0	11	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	67	80	596
United Kingdom	1	1	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	50	66
USA	1	0	147	2	0	0	2	2	0	1	0	8	202
EU27	4	8	12	1	1	0	2	1	3	280	225	0	2823

2.3. Methodology

2.3.1. The GEM-E3-FIT model

To assess GEM-E3-FIT is a large scale multi-sectoral hybrid CGE model designed to evaluate the effects of external shocks on the economy³. The model provides a robust framework to capture the complex energy-economy-climate interactions and simulate the impact of climate and energy policies on the performance of sectors, sectoral output, prices and bilateral trade, the competitiveness of regions and the welfare of communities. Results have a yearly frequency up to 2030 and 5-year time steps until 2050/2100. The model has a global coverage, with 47 regions (see Table 7), where the G-20 countries, EU27 Member States, and major equipment manufacturing or energy exporting countries are represented individually and are also linked through bilateral trade. All countries are linked through endogenous bilateral trade transactions. The model explicitly represents 50 distinct economic activities (see Table 7: Regional resolution of the GEM-E3 model), which are interlinked across the production and consumption value chain.

Focus is placed on the representation of the energy system where specialized bottom-up modules of the power generation, buildings, and transport sectors. To this end, the model includes a detailed representation of the power generation system (12 power technologies) and a detailed transport module (private and public transport modes), while different technological options for energy use in buildings and industry are provided. The energy system representation includes an explicit representation of new technologies such as hydrogen, clean fuels, and bioenergy options.

The GEM-E3-FIR environmental module covers all GHG emissions and a wide range of abatement options, as well as a thoroughly designed carbon market structure (e.g., grandfathering, auctioning, alternative recycling mechanisms). The model has been used extensively by the European Commission, World bank, governments, and public institutions to assess the macroeconomic, distributional and employment implications of the transition to climate neutrality.

The model is based on advanced applied modelling techniques and has been further extended to allow the representation of semi-endogenous technical progress, endogenous formation of labor skills and human capital and a detailed bottom-up representation of the energy system (transport and power generation), along with non-CO₂ emission abatement options and negative emissions technologies. It moves beyond the standard CGE framework as it features involuntary unemployment in the labor market and alternative macroeconomic closures supported by a detailed representation of the financial sector. The model is established on rigorous

³ For a detailed presentation of the model please read <https://e3modelling.com/modelling-tools/gem-e3/> - model manual.

microeconomic theory, it is empirically estimated (substitution and trade elasticities) and can undertake long term analysis as opposed to econometric models that suffer from the Lucas critique. The model can be used both in a comparative and what if analysis frameworks as represents a closed and consistent accounting of resources.

The model is calibrated to a wide range of datasets comprising of IO tables, energy balances, GHG inventories, bilateral trade matrices, investment matrices and household budget surveys. All countries in the model are linked through endogenous bilateral trade transactions identifying origin and destination. The substitution elasticities of the model are not derived from the general literature but are estimated according to its dimensions and functional forms using the latest available datasets. The model is recursive dynamic through the accumulation of capital via the decision for investments and through the accumulation of knowledge stocks via R&D. Model regions are linked through endogenous bilateral trade following the Armington assumption of imperfect substitution across domestic and imported goods. The nested production functions are differentiated by sector and follow a CES structure. For the demand side, the model simulates consumer behavior and maximizes a Klein-Rubin utility function that results in a Linear Expenditure demand system subject to its disposable income not used for obliged consumption (subsistence minima consumption) and after allowing for the decision on savings. The representative household decides on the allocation of its available for consumption income over different consumption categories (COICOP), distinguishing between durable and non-durable goods. The model has been calibrated to the latest statistics (GTAP 11, IEA, UN, ILO) while Eurostat statistics have been used for the EU.

The model is written in a structural form and can be used for the comparative analysis of alternative policy scenarios and the provision of insights on the distributional effects of long-term structural adjustments. In all simulation alternatives the model ensures that the economic system is always in general equilibrium. The GEM-E3 model is written entirely in GAMS. The implementation of the model is split in two stages:

- I. Calibration: At this stage the calculation of the model parameters is carried out so that the model replicates a single year (base year) data.
- II. Scenario quantification: This stage entails model implementation that quantifies a reference and/or a counterfactual scenario.

The most important results, provided by GEM-E3-FIT are: Full Input-Output tables for each country/region identified in the model, GDP and GDP components, employment by economic activity and by skill and unemployment rates, capital, interest rates and investment by country and sector, private and public consumption, bilateral trade flows, consumption matrices by product and investment matrix by ownership branch, GHG emissions by country, sector and fuel and detailed energy system projections

(energy demand by sector and fuel, power generation mix, deployment of transport technologies, energy efficiency improvements).

GEM-E3-FIT enables a thorough understanding and detailed identification of risks and opportunities of the low carbon transition and of the implementation of specific climate and energy policies by capturing:

- Direct impacts on each sector, e.g., how carbon prices and carbon border taxes will affect a sector's costs of production (considering carbon intensity) and thus its production levels (via domestic and international demand);
- Indirect impacts via value chain effects (e.g. changes in prices of intermediate products, of labour and capital inputs), technology costs, consumer preferences, material availability and costs;
- Induced effects via economy feedback, prices, and income implications (e.g. overall drop of demand even for products not directly affected by carbon prices etc.);
- The impacts of financing requirements (capital-intensive process of mitigation) and different financing options;
- Impacts on competitiveness by location site;
- Impacts on sectoral productivity, household incomes and prices due to climate damages.

Table 7: Regional resolution of the GEM-E3 model

Country Code:	Description:	Country Code:	Description:
AUT	Austria	USA	USA
BEL	Belgium	JPN	Japan
BGR	Bulgaria	CAN	Canada
CYP	Cyprus	BRA	Brazil
CRO	Croatia	CHN	China
CZE	Czech Republic	IND	India
DEU	Germany	KOR	South Korea
DNK	Denmark	IDN	Indonesia
ESP	Spain	MEX	Mexico
EST	Estonia	ARG	Argentina
FIN	Finland	TUR	Turkey
FRA	France	SAR	Saudi Arabia
GBR	United Kingdom	OCE	Oceania
GRC	Greece	RUS	Russian federation
HUN	Hungary	ARE	United Arab Emirates
IRL	Ireland	REP	Rest of energy producing countries
ITA	Italy	SAF	South Africa
LTU	Lithuania	REU	Rest of Europe

LUX	Luxembourg	ROW	Rest of the World
LVA	Latvia		
MLT	Malta		
NLD	Netherlands		
POL	Poland		
PRT	Portugal		
SVK	Slovakia		
SVN	Slovenia		
SWE	Sweden		
ROU	Romania		

Table 8: Sectoral resolution of the GEM-E3 model.

Code	Description	Code	Description	Code	Description
Industry		Industry (continued)		Agriculture	
IND01	Ferrous metals	IND19	Equipment for PV panels	AGR01	Agriculture
IND02	Non-ferrous metals	IND20	Equipment for CCS power technology	Services	
IND03	Fabricated Metal products	IND21	CO ₂ Capture	SRV01	Market Services
IND04	Chemical Products	Energy		SRV02	Non Market Services
IND05	Basic pharmaceutical	ENE01	Coal	SRV03	R&D
IND06	Rubber and plastic products	ENE02	Crude Oil	Power Generation	
IND07	Paper products, publishing	ENE03	Oil	PGT01	Coal fired
IND08	Non-metallic minerals	ENE04	Gas	PGT02	Oil fired
IND09	Computer, electronic and optical products	ENE05	Power Supply	PGT03	Gas fired
IND10	Other Equipment Goods	ENE06	Biomass Solid	PGT04	Nuclear
IND11	Transport equipment	ENE07	Biofuels	PGT05	Biomass
IND12	Consumer Goods Industries	ENE08	Hydrogen	PGT06	Hydro electric
IND13	Construction	ENE09	Clean Gas	PGT07	Wind
IND14	Batteries	Transport		PGT08	PV
IND15	EV Transport Equipment	TRA01	Warehousing and support activities	PGT09	Geothermal
IND16	Advanced Electric Appliances	TRA02	Air transport	PGT10	CCS coal

IND17	Advanced Heating and Cooking	TRA03	Land transport	PGT11	CCS Gas
IND18	Equipment for wind power technology	TRA04	Water transport	PGT12	CCS Bio

With respect to the simulation of CBAM implementation in the model the following assumptions are made:

- CBAM is introduced as a tariff which is calculated as the product of the emissions of the exporter multiplied by the difference in carbon price between the two countries
- The model includes a mechanism that endogenizes the extra cost imposed on the exporter. Typically, tariffs do not enter in the optimization problem of the firm as the producer chooses the amount and the type of inputs that minimize its production cost. In the GEM-E3-FIT model the cost of emissions in a specific market (where CBAM is in place), are explicitly considered through carbon taxation and this gives incentives to exporters to adopt more efficient production costs. The additional carbon tax imposed to the exporter is calculated endogenously and is refunded; hence the cost does not pass through to the final consumers.

2.3.2. Scenario design

The impact assessment examines alternative adoption rates of CBAM by major economies. The scenario results are drawn against a reference case which on the macro level is aligned with the most recent projections delivered by IMF, OECD and European Commission for economic variables while demographics and labor market projections are drawn from ILO and UN. With respect to climate ambition, the EU achieves a 55% emission reduction by 2030 in line with the Fit-for-55 package while by 2050 it achieves NETZERO GHG emissions. Non-EU countries are assumed to achieve their NDC targets by 2030, while for the period up to 2050, climate ambition remains constant to the respective one of the NDC.

In total 3 alternative scenarios are quantified, reflecting increasing adoption rates of CBAM measures by major economies. The first scenario assesses the impacts of the EU CBAM, the second scenario assumes that a second group of countries, namely the G1 group including USA, UK, Japan and Australia also adopt carbon border taxes for the same products that are subject to the EU CBAM, while the third scenario assumes that on-top of the G1 group China, India and Canada imposes carbon taxes on imports. The products covered by all the assessed CBAM schemes are specified in the EU CBAM Regulation (EU) 2023/956.

	Reference	NDC+EU CBAM	NDC+G1CBAM	NDC+G2CBAM
EU climate policy	Fit-for-55 extended to net zero GHG to 2050			
Global climate policy	NDC	NDC	NDC	NDC
EU CBAM	No	EU CBAM Regulation (EU) 2023/956	EU CBAM Regulation (EU) 2023/956	EU CBAM Regulation (EU) 2023/956
Other CBAM	No	No	Border Carbon Adjustment schemes in Group 1 countries: Australia, USA, UK and Japan considering domestic carbon pricing schemes or implicit carbon values from emission targets	Border Carbon Adjustment schemes in Group 1 plus Group2 countries: Canada, China and India considering domestic carbon pricing schemes or implicit carbon values from emission targets
Sectors under CBAM	No	Cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, hydrogen, and electricity		

Dynamics in international trade under CBAM, will be largely determined by relative GHG intensities. According to data published the World Bank, most countries and especially India and China are more energy intensive relative to products produced in EU, Japan and USA. This implies that higher tariffs would be imposed in Chinese and Indian products, potentially leading to market share losses.

Table 9: Energy intensity relative to EU27

	Aluminum	Cement	Fertilizers	Iron and steel	Electricity
China	3.37	1.64	2.39	3.22	5.63
India	3.96	1.43	2.82	12.50	3.23
Indonesia	8.29	1.46	1.26	2.70	6.97
Japan	0.70	0.94	0.91	0.78	1.57
Korea, Rep.	0.48	0.99	0.94	1.13	2.74
Australia	4.23	0.91	1.11	1.03	3.00
Turkey	0.95	0.98	1.30	1.66	2.43
United States	0.94	1.08	0.81	1.27	3.21
Canada	1.27	1.15	1.12	2.38	1.20
Brazil	8.06	0.99	0.50	2.32	0.76
United Kingdom	0.22	0.95	0.53	0.77	1.23

Source: World Bank

Another factor that determines the value of the CBAM associated tariffs is the carbon price in the exporting country. The scenario implementation assumes that the CBAM introduction is associated with a domestic carbon pricing scheme, similarly to the EU-ETS, to justify the tariff introduction for climate mitigation purposes. Table 10 presents the carbon value estimated by the model to achieve the respective NDC targets, in the countries of interest. The level of carbon pricing needed to meet the NDC targets is largely related to the emission levels of the assumed baseline scenario, namely the scenario that considers the implementation of currently legislated policies with no achievement of NDCs. For example, Australia would need a relatively high carbon price to achieve its decarbonization targets, while in Turkey and Indonesia the NDC implementation only requires a low carbon price on top of the current policies. The difference between the domestic and importer's carbon price defines the CBAM rate and can lead to higher/lower (export) price increases compared to other countries.

When considering all alternative scenarios, the EU27 imposes the highest tariffs among other major economies, due to the highest domestic carbon price associated with the ambitious NDC and Net zero targets. which is largely explained by the difference in emission targets. EU27 is assumed to achieve NETZERO by 2050, the associated carbon price reaches 403 € per ton emitted while in the non-EU countries, except for Australia and United Kingdom, carbon taxes are lower than 90 € per ton of CO₂ emitted.

Table 10: Carbon price in GEM-E3 reference scenario with NDC implementation (€/ton CO₂)

	2030	2040	2050
China	5	7	8
India	19	28	41
Indonesia	3	4	4
Japan	44	48	51
Korea, Rep.	75	84	88
Australia	146	187	234
Turkey	1	2	3
United States	65	74	84
Canada	35	43	52
Brazil	20	27	36
United Kingdom	226	272	331
EU27	168	286	403

Source: GEM-E3 model

2.4. Results

Macroeconomic impacts will be largely determined by the following main factors: the CBAM burden which depends on sectoral GHG intensity and on the difference on the carbon price levels between the countries subject to CBAM and the ones introducing the CBAM, the bilateral trade pattern and the relative importance of CBAM related sectors in the domestic economy and downstream cost differentials.

Global GDP impacts are found to be small in all scenarios examined. In the EUCBAM, GDP changes range between -0.02% to -0.09%, in CBAMG1 from -0.02% to -0.10% and in CBAMG2 from -0.02% to -0.11%. The effects are minimal in 2030 in all scenarios examined and they grow in magnitude from 2035, when CBAM is fully implemented, and aggravate over time as climate ambition, hence carbon taxes, increase. Global trade is projected to be slightly affected by the adoption of CBAM measures by major economies. Overall exports are projected to decrease by 0.1% in EUCBAM scenario and by 0.14% and 0.15% in CBAMG1 and CBAMG2 respectively.

Turkey, the EU and India record the highest GDP changes among the countries examined. EU27 is found to be better off in CBAMG1 and CBAMG2 compared to the EUCBAM scenario, with cumulative (2025-2050) GDP losses being equal to 0.0033% in the former scenario (or 154 bn.€) compared to 0.0035% (or approximately 147 bn.€). Still the magnitude of impacts is very limited. This finding is associated with the adoption of CBAM by other countries which leads to competitiveness gains of EU-based products in the global market due to their lower GHG emission intensity. The same holds for USA, where GDP losses are found to be lower in CBAMG2 compared to CBAMG1 (-13.4 bn.€ compared to -15 bn.€).

Figure 1: GDP changes compared to the reference scenario in 2035 and in 2050 (%)

Source: GEM-E3-FIT model

The impact assessment reveals differences in the drivers of GDP changes among countries examined. Figure 2 presents the decomposition of GDP impacts by its components for the largest global economies. This decomposition considers both the magnitude of change compared to the reference scenario but also the magnitude of each component in GDP. While trade is affected the most in relative terms, the decomposition of GDP impacts indicated that In EU27, Japan and S. Korea impacts are driven primarily by exports, while in the rest of the countries the effects are driven by changes in households' consumption. The latter can be an induced economic effect of lower incomes, which as a main contributor of GDP can drive impacts despite minimal changes compared to the reference levels. Further, a common finding for most countries is that imports fall as a response to CBAM measures, either due to the competitiveness improvement of domestically produced products or as a direct consequence of lower available incomes and higher prices for the composite goods.

The latter can also be the case not only in countries implementing CBAM but also in countries subject to CBAM that are importers of goods from the first group of countries.

Differences in sectoral responses reflecting production specificities (import dependence, production structure etc.) are outlined by the impact assessment. At the sectoral level, iron and steel responds more intensively in the imposition of carbon border taxes, compared to other sectors subject to CBAM. In India GDP losses are driven mainly by iron and steel, also indirectly affecting the intermediate demand and production of the fossil fuel sector, while in Türkiye non-metallic minerals (which include cement) and chemicals (which include fertilizers) are the sectors mostly impacted.

In EU27, GDP losses are associated to the change in competitiveness of downstream processes. Higher overall input costs, driven by CBAM tariffs, hinder the competitiveness of non-CBAM related sectors. For example, in 2050 in the EUCBAM scenario, export in non-CBAM manufacturing sectors fall by 1.1% compared to the reference and imports of those products increase by 0.75%. This is further amplified by the slightly negative income implications to the EU trading partners due to the imposition of the border adjustments. This leads to production losses which counterbalance the positive effect of the CBAM on energy intensive industries. Furthermore, due to differences in the labor intensity of sectors, employment and hence labor income, falls (-0.05%).

In India economic impacts are primarily driven by the lower exports, hence activity of the ferrous metals industry. On average cumulative production falls by 9% across scenarios, with the highest loss recorded in the EUCBAM (-10%). Lower production of the iron and steel sector is propagated in the economy through the energy channel, and energy sectors face decreased demand for their products in particular the oil and coal sector. In Türkiye, in addition to iron and steel changes are also driven by reductions in the non-metallic minerals sector (which includes cement), for which Turkey is one of the largest exporters worldwide. On average, exports of CBAM-related industries fall by 5.4% in the EUCBAM scenario, and by 6.4% in CBAMG1 and the CBAMG2 scenario, while total exports fall by 0.2% to 0.3%. Labor and capital income falls as activity decreases and household consumption falls. In China the high differentiation in exporting destination coupled with the largest exporting sectors are not the energy intensive ones, such as consumer goods and other equipment goods, leads to minimal GDP impacts. China along with USA and Canada record the lowest impacts among the countries that are negatively affected.

In Japan and S. Korea, the increase in GDP is driven primarily by the iron and steel sector, which is characterized by relatively lower CO₂ intensity compared to the rest of the non-EU countries, hence the implementation of CBAM yields competitiveness

increases for products produced there. Higher activity leads to higher investments and higher income, which is translated into higher consumption.

Figure 2: Decomposition of GDP changes (% change from reference)

Source: GEM-E3-FIT

In terms of total exports the effects are more profound in EU27, India and Turkey across all three alternative scenarios. In the EU exports fall between 0.58% (or 578

billion €) to to 0.56% (or 555 billion €) in cumulative terms as intermediate goods become more expensive for the production of all goods and services, affecting their competitiveness, primarily so of manufacturing goods that are not subject to CBAM (Figure 3). The impacts are higher in the EUCBAM scenario and lessen as more countries introduce CBAMs, as this improves the relative competitiveness of EU products. However, the EU has the most notable losses in total exports across all scenarios, also due to the highest imposed CBAM rate as explained by the regional carbon price differences. For a number of other regions, including China, Brazil and India, the negative effects of EU-CBAM and CBAM expansion can be counterbalanced by increasing exports of goods not subject to CBAM (Figure 3).

India and Turkey are particularly sensitive to the imposition of carbon tariffs from the EU27 due to their relatively high emission intensity (India) and due to the overall trade volume with the EU (Turkey). The United Kingdom records export gains in the case of EUCBAM, which fade when more countries adopt the CBAM and turn into losses in CBAMG1 and CBAMG2 scenarios. Sectoral exports can also be affected in a different manner in each of the three scenarios, as for example in the case of Canada, who once key trading partners like the USA enforce a CBAM, see an overall reduction of exports primarily due to declining exports of CBAM products, while in the EUCBAM scenario exports registered an increase. Fossil fuel exports are also affected indirectly as intermediate goods for the production of CBAM products, and can be one of the main driver of export changes in countries like Indonesia, Australia and the USA.

Table 11: Exports change in alternative scenarios (% from reference)

		2030	2050	Cumulative
EUCBAM	China	0.00%	0.02%	0.01%
	India	-0.26%	-0.32%	-0.31%
	Indonesia	-0.01%	0.00%	0.00%
	Japan	0.02%	0.07%	0.05%
	Korea, Rep.	0.02%	0.03%	0.02%
	Australia	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
	Turkey	-0.11%	-0.37%	-0.26%
	United States	0.01%	0.03%	0.02%
	Canada	0.02%	0.05%	0.04%
	Brazil	-0.02%	-0.04%	-0.04%
	United Kingdom	0.04%	0.11%	0.08%
	EU27	-0.38%	-0.89%	-0.66%
			2030	2050
CBAMG1	China	0.00%	-0.01%	-0.01%
	India	-0.26%	-0.37%	-0.36%
	Indonesia	-0.01%	-0.06%	-0.06%

Japan	0.02%	0.02%	0.01%
Korea, Rep.	0.02%	0.04%	0.03%
Australia	0.00%	-0.22%	-0.16%
Turkey	-0.11%	-0.44%	-0.31%
United States	0.01%	-0.05%	-0.04%
Canada	0.02%	-0.05%	-0.04%
Brazil	-0.02%	-0.07%	-0.06%
United Kingdom	0.04%	-0.03%	-0.02%
EU27	-0.38%	-0.86%	-0.63%

	2030	2050	Cumulative
China	0.00%	-0.02%	-0.02%
India	-0.26%	-0.46%	-0.42%
Indonesia	-0.01%	-0.10%	-0.08%
Japan	0.02%	0.03%	0.01%
Korea, Rep.	0.02%	0.04%	0.04%
Australia	0.00%	-0.22%	-0.15%
Turkey	-0.11%	-0.44%	-0.31%
United States	0.01%	-0.05%	-0.04%
Canada	0.02%	-0.08%	-0.06%
Brazil	-0.02%	-0.07%	-0.06%
United Kingdom	0.04%	-0.03%	-0.01%
EU27	-0.38%	-0.86%	-0.63%

CBAMG2

Source: GEM-E3-FIT

Figure 3: Decomposition of cumulative export changes

Source: GEM-E3-FIT

In EUCBAM scenario, we identify two group of countries according to their export performance: i) the first group consists of China, India, Indonesia, Brazil and Turkey and records a reduction in CBAM-related exports, and ii) a second group which consists of USA, Canada, Japan, Korea and Australia that records increase in their exports. The most affected country is India, where CBAM exports fall by approximately 23% in cumulative terms (2030-2050) compared to the reference scenario (Figure 4). Exports to EU27 fall by 15%, while exports to the Rest of the World (ROW) fall by 5%. The second most impacted country, by the implementation of CBAM in the EU27, is Turkey with overall CBAM exports falling cumulatively by 9% with export flows to the EU27 accounting for more than 80% of the assessed change. A share of the EU27 market lost by products of Southeast Asian countries and Turkey is

partly taken by goods produced in United Kingdom, USA, Australia, and to a lower extent in Japan and Korea.

Finally, the assessment shows an increase in the exports of some countries (e.g., Canada, Korea etc.) towards USA and India (e.g., USA, Japan, Indonesia, Australia etc.). In the case of US, there is a shift of the importer's mix (i.e. countries which export to the US), as Indian and Turkish products are losing market share which shifts to Canada, and S. Korea. While higher exports to India are related to the overall competitiveness losses recorded by the Indian industry. These losses are induced by the CBAM signal: when EU27 imposes tariffs based on emission content, producers outside the EU adopt, to a certain extent, greener production processes to minimize the impacts of the tariff on the final price of their products. Hence, upwards changes in the production cost can be expected in countries outside the EU27 (due to additional capital costs and potential fuel switch).

Figure 4: Bilateral trade changes in CBAM products by country – EUCBAM

In CBAMG1, exports to EU27 continue to be a significant driver of total export change in iron and steel, aluminum, fertilizers and cement, in most of the countries. The most noticeable change is recorded in Canada, as overall CBAM exports decrease in CBAMG1 by 2.2% (Figure 5) compared to an increase of 0.9% in EUCBAM. As USA is the most important trade partner of Canada the unilateral adoption of CBAM hinders trade performance of Canadian CBAM related industries. The adoption of carbon adjustment from the US implies benefits for United Kingdom, Australia, and Japan which are projected to increase their exports to the US market and losses for exporters located in China, and India.

With respect to trade changes associated with the introduction of CBAM in Australia, China and Indonesia are mostly affected with exports of CBAM products recording a loss of 0.7% and 1.5% respectively compared to the reference scenario over the projection period (0% in the EUCBAM scenario). The implementation of carbon tariffs in Japan mainly affects goods of Chinese and Indian origin which record cumulative

losses of 0.5% and 0.4% respectively (the respective changes in the EUCBAM are 0% and -0.2%).

Figure 5: Bilateral trade changes in CBAM products by country – CBAMG1

Source: GEM-E3-FIT model

Moving to the CBAMG2 scenario (Figure 6), where CBAM is also introduced by China, India and Canada, we find that the most important changes are found in China and India, as there are significant bilateral trade flows with high emission content. Chinese and Indonesian exports to India record losses, while exports of (primarily) Japan and South Korea increase by 0.7% and 1.5% with respect to the reference throughout the projection period. The respective change in the CBAMG1 scenario is found to be equal to 0.5% and 1.0%. In China the introduction of CBAM has important implications for Indonesian products as their imports decreases by 1.3% cumulatively compared to a reduction of 0.3% in CBAMG1.

China - CBAMG2

India - CBAMG2

Indonesia - CBAMG2

Turkey - CBAMG2

Japan - CBAMG2

Korea - CBAMG2

Figure 6: Bilateral trade changes in CBAM products by country – CBAMG2

2.5. Conclusions

The impact of the adoption of CBA measures by major global economies were examined with the use of a global CGE model, GEM-E3-FIT. The impacts of alternative CBAM adoption rates on GDP and emissions are found to be low, with global GDP impacts ranging from 0.02% to 0.07% while the impacts on emission reductions are also weak. If most of the greater economies adopt CBAM global emissions would reduce by a mere 0.6% compared to a reference case with no CBAM.

In the field of international trade, the adoption of “carbon tariffs” will introduce an important factor in the determination of product competitiveness in global markets, that of carbon content. Advanced economies have already or are more likely to adopt production methods with lower carbon footprint in energy intensive industries compared to (for example) economies like China and India. Competitive advantage in the latter comes primarily from wage and capital cost differentials while production in energy intensive industry is also linked cheap fossil fuel energy. The adoption of CBAM by Europe for example, would imply higher costs for this type of producers and would lead to a shift in EU suppliers from Chinese and Indian to Japanese, S. Korean and USA.

In terms of effectiveness of CBAM policies in delivering economic benefits is put at stake by increased production costs, which propagate to non-protected sectors yielding competitiveness losses which almost counterbalance increased activity in energy intensive industries. For example, in EU27 we find that in all three scenarios examined, losses in other industrial sectors account for approximately more than 78% of the production gains recorded in energy intensive industries.

Overall, the countries that are found to be more vulnerable to the implementation of CBAM are those with high emission intensity and a low domestic carbon pricing. Both elements imply an increase of the CBAM burden and higher competitiveness losses. In this category fall countries like India, Turkey and China.

2.6. References

- Bao, Q., Tang, L., Zhang, Z. X., & Wang, S. (2013). Impacts of border carbon adjustments on China’s sectoral emissions: Simulations with a dynamic computable general equilibrium model. *China Economic Review*, 24(1), 77–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chieco.2012.11.002>
- Chu, H. L., Do, N. T., Nguyen, L., Le, L., Ho, Q. A., Dang, K., & Ta, M. A. (2024). The economic impacts of the European Union’s Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism on developing countries: the case of Vietnam. *Fulbright Review of Economics and Policy*, 4(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1108/frep-03-2024-0011>

- Gu, R., Guo, J., Huang, Y., & Wu, X. (2023). Impact of the EU carbon border adjustment mechanism on economic growth and resources supply in the BASIC countries. *Resources Policy*, 85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2023.104034>
- Mattoo, A., Subramanian, A., van der Mensbrugghe, D., & He, J. (2013). Trade effects of alternative carbon border-tax schemes. *Review of World Economics*, 149(3), 587–609. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10290-013-0159-0>
- Rocchi, P., Lobato, E. C., di Bella, A., & Bosetti, V. (n.d.). *Expanding carbon pricing boundaries and the EU CBAM: insights into China and India*.
- Siy, A. L., Wang, A., Zheng, T., & Hu, X. (2023). Research on the Impact of the EU's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism: Based on the GTAP Model. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15064761>
- Takeda, S., & Arimura, T. H. (2024). A computable general equilibrium analysis of the EU CBAM for the Japanese economy. *Japan and the World Economy*, 70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japwor.2024.101242>
- Zhu, J., Zhao, Y., & Zheng, L. (2024). The Impact of the EU Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism on China's Exports to the EU. *Energies*, 17(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17020509>

3. Environmental and economic impacts of EU CBAM and SBCE on the competitiveness of the main Brazilian commodities on the international market

3.1. Introduction

As a developing country, Brazil relies heavily on the exports of primary goods to control monetary policy and obtain foreign currency on the international market. The main products on Brazil's exports list are crude oil, soybeans and iron ore, which are transported by sea and their main destinations are China, the countries of the European Union (EU) and the USA.

International maritime transport is a major contributor to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, accounting for approximately 3% of total global emissions (Torreglosa et al., 2022). In the absence of measures to mitigate emissions, this mode of transport is expected to increase CO₂ emissions by 17% by 2050 (Christodoulou et al., 2021).

As the sector is not part of the Paris Agreement, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has taken on the role of promoting policies to reduce emissions. In 2018, IMO member countries adopted an initial strategy with the aim of reducing the sector's absolute GHG emissions by 50% by 2050 compared to 2008 levels, with a subsequent review in 2023 to achieve net zero emissions by 2050 (Serra and Fancelo, 2020; Müller-Casseres et al., 2024). To achieve these targets, they pointed out that the adoption of low-emission alternative fuels was necessary, as well as market-based measures (MBM), including carbon pricing mechanisms and border adjustments to prevent carbon leakage.

Among the MBM options adopted by the EU as part of the revision of their Emissions Trading System, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) requires importers of selected energy-intensive commodities to purchase emission reduction certificates. Among the relevant commodities exported by Brazil, CBAM will initially only cover iron ore (iron and steel sector), although there is nothing to prevent it from covering crude oil and soybeans in the future, the former due to the energy-intensity associated with extraction and the latter due to the association with deforestation to expand the area used to produce soybeans.

In terms of international trade, the mechanism has been associated with protectionist barriers to European industry (Rocchi et al., 2024), which could lead to disputes at the WTO level. The main exporting countries, especially the emerging and developing economies, share this concern, as is the case of Brazil.

Therefore, this work complements the analysis carried out by Rocchi et al (2024), by measuring the impacts of CBAM and the Brazilian carbon pricing policy on the country's emissions and GDP. In addition, it assesses the extent to which the profitability of Brazil's commodity sectors is affected by policies to respond to the impacts of carbon pricing, in terms of reducing the energy intensity of commodity transportation routes to EU countries. To carry out this analysis, the computable general equilibrium (CGE) model PAEG (Gurgel, 2013; Nazareth et al., 2017) was used, with the GTAP 11 database.

3.2. Methodology

As previously mentioned, the PAEG model was used to estimate the impacts of EU CBAM and Brazil's SBCE. The PAEG (General Equilibrium Analysis Project) is an applied general equilibrium tool capable of representing a global macroeconomic multi-sectoral multi-regional model built on GTAP 11 database and designed to analyze interactions across countries and sectors.

Furthermore, as well as in the GTAPinGAMS model, a simple additional assumption is made investment demand and international capital flows are considered exogenously

fixed at the base year level. Thus, changes in the real exchange rate must occur to accommodate changes in export and import flows aftershocks, keeping the balance of payments constant. In Teixeira et al. (2013) we find the complete description of the behavioral and equilibrium equations of the PAEG model and its original sources: GTAP and GTAPinGAMS.

Like Rocchi et al (2024), CBAM was introduced through a tariff on commodity imports. This tariff depends on the direct carbon intensity of the imported goods, the EU carbon price and the phase-in percentage of CBAM, factors that evolve over time. In addition, the SBCE's carbon pricing is assumed to be 40 euros per tCO₂, and free allowances are being phased out similarly under the EU ETS. These measures have an impact on the cost of energy commodities used in the production processes, thus influencing both trade patterns and emission levels.

The PAEG model has been updated with the GTAP 11 database, in which Brazil is a representative region. Therefore, the data used to calibrate the model refers, in the case of Brazil, to 2015 input-output information updated, using the RAS method, with data from the Brazilian System of National Accounts for 2022. Detailed information on calibration procedures and input data, as well as model characteristics, will be provided as supplementary data associated with a final paper still under preparation by the authors, by the time this paper is submitted for review in an international journal.

In terms of scenario assumptions, to be comparable and complement the work of Rocchi et al (2024), the population growth and labor productivity variables from the SSP2 database are assumed to be exogenous in the baseline. In addition, it is assumed that EU ETS allowances are auctioned in their entirety in the electricity sector, while in the industrial sectors the free allocation of allowances is phased out according to the scheme presented in the ETS review (EPC, 2023).

Different policy scenarios were then evaluated, and three different policies (individually or combined) were modeled. Initially, the adoption of CBAM in the iron and steel, aluminum, fertilizer, cement, soybean and crude oil sectors was considered. Pricing was modeled for the same sectors under the SBCE, assuming a carbon price of 40 euros per tonne of CO₂. Although the SBCE does not currently plan to cover the agricultural commodities sector, soybean pricing was adopted to assess the extent to which this product would be affected in international trade under the Chinese, EU and Indian emissions trading systems.

Table 12: Carbon pricing policies implemented by scenario

Scenarios	Policies implemented
Baseline	Full EU ETS
CBAM	Full EU ETS and EU CBAM (sectors covered: iron and steel, aluminum, fertilizers, cement, crude oil, and soybeans)
Brazilian SBCE + CBAM	Full EU ETS, CBAM and Brazilian SBCE on energy-intensive industries (the SBCE will be gradual and divided into five main phases, covering industrial facilities that emit more than 25,000 tCO ₂ eq per year). A carbon price up to 40 EUR per tonne of CO ₂ is assumed (Rocchi et al., 2024).

3.3. Results

This section In terms of the impact on emissions of the introduction of CBAM on EU countries, Brazil (BR) and in total terms in all economies (TOT), particularly on energy-intensive industries, there are modest effects in terms of CO₂ emissions, which corroborates the study by Rocchi et al (2024). A slight increase in CO₂ emissions is observed (Figure 7), which can be attributed to an increase in production activity which, in turn, leads to a proportional increase in emissions from energy-intensive commodities.

Figure 7: CO₂ emissions variation in the CBAM scenario (Brazil, EU countries and Total)

The analysis of the impacts of the CBAM policy on GDP revealed insignificant impacts for Brazil, the EU countries and the rest of the world economy. However, given the representativeness of the primary commodity sectors in shaping Brazil's GDP, the negative impacts on GDP were around three times higher than those seen in China by Rocchi et al (2024).

Figure 8: GDP variation in the CBAM scenario (Brazil, EU countries and Total)

In turn, the main impacts of CBAM are on the profitability associated with exports of Brazil's main commodities, namely crude oil, soybeans and iron ore. In the case of the margin associated with crude oil exports, Petrobras (Brazil's national oil company) showed a strong increase in its operating margin in 2024, which would allow it to deal with the small drop in profitability compared to that of the CBAM scenario. Furthermore, the European market is not the main destination for Brazil's exports. Soybeans and iron ore would potentially be most affected in terms of profitability. However, exports generally have prices established in long-term contracts, and mostly go to the Chinese market, which requires this instrument to guarantee the supply of these inputs.

Figure 9: Export profitability variation in the exports of crude oil, soybean and iron ore from Brazil

Similar to the approach adopted by Rocchi et al (2024), the changes in GDP and CO₂ emissions compared to the baseline scenario are evaluated, considering the application of the policies listed in Table 12. Figure 10 shows the change in CO₂ emissions and the change in GDP for Brazil, Europe and the rest of the world.

The impacts in terms of emissions and GDP for Brazil differ significantly from the impacts of implementing CBAM shown in Figures 7 and 8. By adopting the SBCE, Brazil could achieve a total CO₂ emissions reduction of around 11% by 2050. The global variation in CO₂ emissions is also responsible for the increase in emissions recorded in other regions, such as the EU. As Brazilian commodities now have an implicit carbon cost, they become less competitive and, as a result, EU production increases and has slightly higher costs in relation to the baseline.

Figure 10: Impacts of alternative scenarios of CO₂ and GDP (Brazil, EU countries and rest of world)

As expected, reducing emissions entails an economic cost captured in terms of GDP. The carbon cost increases production costs, which in the case of Brazil implies in a loss of GDP of 4% in 2050.

3.4. Conclusions

From an environmental point of view, a carbon pricing policy fulfills the role of mitigating emissions. However, the expected reduction is small, especially given the challenge associated with the effectiveness of the policy in terms of reducing emissions in sectors that are difficult to mitigate, such as international maritime transport. In this regard, sectoral mitigation policies associated with tax incentives, such as the Brazilian Future Fuel Law – *Lei do Combustível do Futuro* (BRAZIL, 2025), can complement carbon pricing policies in sectors with emissions that are difficult to mitigate.

With regards to the impacts on GDP and export profitability, our results highlight that the current design of the CBAM policy has insignificant implications (impacts on GDP always less than 0.5%) for both EU and non-EU countries, becoming more relevant for the profitability of exports of the main Brazilian commodities. Therefore, our modeling shows that CBAM and SBCE have a pronounced impact on the production and international trade of commodities, especially in energy-intensive sectors that depend on international maritime transport. In this regard, sector-specific compensatory measures should be planned accordingly, such as border adjustments.

The impacts estimated in this modeling exercise therefore revealed that the fear of loss of profitability associated with exporting of Brazil's agricultural commodities to EU member countries is valid. However, the effect in terms of lost GDP is relatively small, and the environmental compensation (emissions mitigation) is significant. In addition, carbon markets are promoting research efforts and redirecting attention to carbon pricing as one of the pillars of climate action.

In other words, trade measures that potentially affect competitiveness should be seen as a component of the broader climate policy framework, designed to promote carbon pricing and industrial decarbonization (Rocchi et al., 2024).

3.5. References

BRAZIL (2025). Lei do Combustível do Futuro. Available: <https://www.gov.br/planalto/pt-br/acompanhe-o-planalto/noticias/2024/10/presidente-lula-sanciona-lei-do-combustivel-do-futuro-para-promover-a-mobilidade-sustentavel#:~:text=0%20Combust%C3%ADvel%20do%20Futuro%20prev%C3%AA,de%20gases%20de%20efeito%20estufa>.

- Christodoulou, A., Dalaklis, D., Ölçer, A.I., Ballini, F., 2021. Can market-based measures stimulate investments in green Technologies for the abatement of ghg emissions from shipping? a review of proposed market-based measures. *Transactions on Maritime Science*. doi:10.7225/toms.v10.n01.017.
- European Parliament and Council (EPC), 2023. Directive (EU) 2023/959 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 amending Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and Decision (EU) 2015/1814 concerning the establishment and operation of a market stability reserve for the Union greenhouse gas emission trading system. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/959/oj>.
- Gurgel, A.C. PAEG “Hands On” Instalação e Execução do Programa PAEG. PAEG Technical Paper No. 5 Versão revisada em Dezembro 2013. Available: https://paeg.ufv.br/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/2013_PAEG_Hands.pdf.
- Müller-Casseres, E., Leblanc, F., van den Berg, M. et al., 2024. International shipping in a world below 2 °C. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 14, 600–607. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-024-01997-1>.
- Nazareth, M.E., Gurgel, A.C., Vieira, W.C. Fiscal decentralization and economic performance in brazil: an investigation using PAEG/GTAP. 20th Annual Conference on Global Economic Analysis. West Lafayette, Indiana, United States, July 2017.
- Rocchi, P. and Lobato, E. Campo and Di Bella, A. and Bosetti, V., Expanding Carbon Pricing Boundaries and the EU Cbam: Insights into China and India. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4997200> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4997200>
- Serra, P., Fancello, G., 2020. Towards the imo’s ghg goals: A critical overview of the perspectives and challenges of the main options for decarbonizing international shipping. *Sustainability* doi:10.3390/su12083220.
- Teixeira, E. C.; Pereira, M. W. G.; Gurgel, A. C. (2013). *A Estrutura do PAEG*. Campo Grande: Life Editora.
- Torreglosa, J.P., González-Rivera, E., García-Triviño, P., Vera, D., 2022. Performance analysis of a hybrid electric ship by real-time verification. *Energies* doi:10.3390/en15062116.

4. Expanding carbon pricing boundaries and the EU CBAM: insights into China and India

4.1. Introduction

Initially proposed in Ursula von der Leyen's agenda (von der Leyen, 2019), the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) has emerged as a key measure of the European Green Deal (EGD). After two years of legislative process, the European Parliament endorsed this policy tool in April 2023 (European Parliament and Council, 2023a). CBAM consists of tariffs applied to selected carbon-intensive commodities imported into the European Union (EU). Although the nature and purpose of this policy can be multifaceted, the European Commission (EC) consistently underscores its primary objective of addressing climate concerns. Specifically, CBAM is designed to avoid or mitigate carbon leakage and encourage cleaner industrial production in non-EU countries. Carbon leakage indicates a situation when, as a consequence of a country's unilateral policy aiming at carbon emission reduction, other countries' emissions increase given laxer regulations. This can be due to a change in prices, the relocation of polluting firms outside the country imposing stringent climate policy or an increase in imports.

The need to limit carbon leakages has become more relevant as, concurrently, the EC has planned to strengthen their existing Emissions Trading System (ETS). The ETS is a compliance carbon market based on a cap-and-trade system of emissions allowances for energy-intensive industries, power generation and the aviation sector. Since 2013, power production installations across Europe have faced full auctioning as the default method of allocating emission allowances. Still, industries characterised as emissions-intensive and trade-exposed (EITE) have been spared from the ETS auctioning thus far. This is set to change, as the recent revision for the ongoing fourth phase of the ETS, which will span until 2030, envisages the phase-out of free allowances for the industrial sectors. Regulated installations will gradually be required to surrender sufficient allowances to balance their total emissions (European Parliament and Council, 2023b). To apply imports the same treatment as EU products, ensuring WTO compliance, the CBAM will be introduced in conjunction with the phasing out of free ETS allowances. Thus, EU importers will be required, as of 2026, to purchase certificates equivalent to the weekly EU carbon price. The initial coverage will include five sectors: iron and steel, cement, aluminium, fertilisers, hydrogen and electricity (European Parliament and Council, 2023a).

The EU CBAM is set to allow partial or full exemptions from the levy when a carbon price has already been "effectively paid" in the country of origin for the declared embedded emissions. This provision found in Article 46 is crucial in encouraging countries outside the EU ETS to take up a carbon pricing regime and reduce

emissions in a cost-effective manner. When faced with the trade-off, the foreign nation might prefer to retain the revenues collected within its borders while reducing compliance costs rather than surrender the tariff to the EU. Else they might use other policies, such as bans or standards to reduce embedded emissions and again limit or eliminate the need to surrender the tariff to the EU.

The EU's proposal for a CBAM marks a critical juncture in climate policymaking as it directly addresses the fragmented and uncoordinated nature of carbon pricing mechanisms worldwide. Since its proposal in 2021, and even more since its approval, the CBAM has stirred considerable academic and institutional debate, focusing on its efficacy in mitigating carbon leakage and preserving competitiveness (Böhringer et al., 2022) without breaching international trade laws (Espa et al., 2022). For instance, the current design issues at stake revolve around the coverage of sectors (Kolev, 2021), their default values for emissions (Vidovic et al., 2023), the implications for exports (Marcu et al., 2024), the revenue use (Beaufils, et al., 2023, Delbeke et al., 2021), the risk of retaliation from other countries (Clora et al., 2023; Overland and Sabyrbekov, 2022) and the potential regressive effects within EU trading partners (Fredriksson and Zachmann, 2021) and across (Magacho et al., 2024).

Moreover, the introduction of CBAM has sparked significant reactions in the political sphere, even though its full implementation is still a decade away. On the international stage, the mechanism has met wide criticisms from outsiders labelling it a veiled protectionist move favouring European industries, lifting “green trade barriers” and operating contrary to the spirit of the Paris Agreement (Sun et al., 2024). Major exporting countries, mainly emerging and developing economies, have shared concerns over the EU's intentions and may wish to pursue disputes at the WTO level. However, in line with the CBAM's initial objectives, a surge in discussions and commitments to establish domestic carbon markets has emerged (IETA, 2024). This renewed momentum behind carbon pricing has seen large middle-income countries such as Brazil, India, Indonesia, Chile, Colombia, and Turkey making notable progress, contributing to the increasing global adoption of such instruments (World Bank, 2024a).

Given the framework described above, the goal of this paper is twofold. Firstly, we aim to analyse the expected environmental and macroeconomic impact of the EU CBAM policy according to the specific scope and time frame delineated by the legislative text currently approved. Prior to the policy's approval, numerous analyses were conducted regarding its potential impacts and ramifications, taking into account hypothetical policy designs (Böhringer et al., 2018, Cosbey et al., 2012; Lanzi et al., 2012; Mehling et al., 2019; Weitzel et al., 2012). It is now possible to move from theoretical conjecture to empirical ex-ante evaluation, assessing the actual design of the policy along with its implications for EU countries and foreign trade partners. Observing the macroeconomic and environmental impact of the CBAM in its current design can

shed light on possible reasons for the several international reactions that the instrument seems to have raised. Secondly, given the multiple emissions control policies that different countries are considering—measures that, triggered by nations’ long-term climate objectives, may have been accelerated by the EU’s agenda—this paper seeks to analyse CBAM in the context of mitigation measures that could potentially enable non-EU countries to secure an exemption from the EU CBAM. The hypothesis underpinning this analysis is not that these policies are a direct reaction to the CBAM since many countries have already activated the political processes to implement emission reduction policies. However, there appears to be a growing trend of interactions and synergies among efforts to promote and align carbon pricing policies (Delbeke and Vis, 2023). Additionally, the potential to obtain CBAM tariff exemptions and the interest in maintaining trade relations with the EU has catalysed further support.

We focus our attention on China and India, in particular, for several reasons. First, they are countries strongly oriented towards exports, with Europe being one of their main trading partners in CBAM-covered sectors. Conversely, these two countries are significant trading partners for the EU, accounting for approximately 20% of the total EU imports of the main CBAM products (Figure 11).

Figure 11: CBAM trade dependence. Export shares to EU versus EU import shares from China and India.

Source: own elaboration based on UN Comtrade (2024) data.

Second, they are the top two global producers of steel, collectively accounting for over 60% of crude steel production, with China dominating the majority share (World Steel Associations, 2024). China and India are nowadays among the main contributors to global carbon emissions, placing in the top five and generating 12.6 and 2.6 GtCO₂

respectively in 2022, which together make up about 40% of the world's total annual emissions (Crippa et al., 2023). Their industries account for a considerable amount of emissions due to the widespread use of coal-based production processes (Figure 12). Consequently, given their high carbon intensities, CBAM would place them at a competitive disadvantage with respect to cleaner exporters.

Figure 12: CBAM exposure. CO₂ emissions intensities of selected commodities, China, India and the EU.

Source: own elaboration based on World Bank (2024b) data.

Finally, both are showing some willingness to implement more stringent policies to reduce CO₂ emissions. In 2020, China pledged to have CO₂ emissions peak before 2030 and become carbon neutral by 2060 (UNFCCC, 2021a). On the other hand, India is aiming to cut their emission intensity by 45% in 2030, compared to 2005, and reach net-zero in 2070 (UNFCCC, 2021b). To meet these goals, both have proven open to embracing market-based instruments as mitigation policies such as emissions trading schemes (Table 13).

Table 13: Overview of Chinese and Indian compliance carbon markets

Policy	Chinese ETS	Indian Carbon Credit Trading Scheme
Timeline	Launched in 2021 following the implementation of eight regional pilots which have been running since the early 2010s.	A 2022 amendment bill provides the legal basis to establish an Indian Carbon Market (ICM) and the issuance of carbon credit certificates for the reduction of emissions.
Sectoral coverage	Coal and gas-fired power plants with annual emissions of at least 26 ktCO ₂ . While power generation has transitioned to the national scheme, some provincial markets still encompass other sectors.	Current plans foresee a compliance scheme covering energy-intensive industrial sectors. The market will be based on the existing Perform, Achieve and Trade scheme – a mandatory energy

		efficiency scheme covering more than 1000 entities from 13 sectors.
Allowance allocation	Allowances are distributed for free using emission intensity benchmarking. The emissions cap is the aggregate of total allowances and changes according to the actual production levels.	The obligated entities will receive an annual emissions intensity target covering a three-year trajectory period.
Next steps	Interim Regulations clarify that auctioning is set to be introduced and gradually expanded. The scope is expected to be gradually expanded to cover seven other sectors: petrochemicals, chemicals, building materials, steel, nonferrous metals, paper, and domestic aviation.	It is expected that a phased transition from the current scheme to the compliance carbon market will begin in 2024.

Source: own elaboration based on ICAP (2024).

These policies have been tailored to fit country-specific economic, industrial and political contexts. However, it is possible to hypothesise that any recent updates to their carbon pricing policies are partly driven by an interest to access the CBAM exemption.

Given the objective of the paper to analyse the macroeconomic and environmental impact of the CBAM and possible Chinese and Indian carbon prices in an international trade context, we employ the general equilibrium model FIDELIO (Fully Interregional Dynamic Econometric Long-term Input-Output) (Rocchi et. al, 2024). Developed by the EU Joint Research Centre, FIDELIO is a multi-region multi-sectoral neo-Keynesian recursive dynamic macroeconomic model. This tool is particularly suitable for our analysis as it captures the main channels through which the policies are expected to impact the economies of the involved countries. In particular, multi-region multi-sectoral models can assess the impact of the policies on both the directly targeted commodities and industries, as well as all other sectors using those commodities as inputs, capturing spillover and rebound effects. Additionally, they can model the impacts of policies like the CBAM or alternative domestic policies on relative prices, international trade flows, production, and income distribution.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 4.2 describes the relevant literature. Section 4.3 provides an overview of the model, the methodology, the main data used and the scenarios analysed. Section 4.4 describes the results, while Section 5 draws some policy implications and conclusions. Sector of interest? (Industry? Reflect on plan)

4.2. Literature review

Carbon border adjustments are considered an effective tool to mitigate competitive disadvantages and prevent carbon leakage caused by stringent unilateral climate regulations in energy-intensive and trade-exposed industries. Early academic research focused on the designing of a CBAM to complement domestic carbon prices, implying that such mechanisms would equalise the cost of carbon across borders, thus levelling the playing field between producers and importers (Böhringer et al., 2010).

Before the EU formalised the CBAM, the literature made varying assumptions about its design in order to inform policymakers on its potential effectiveness. Since then, the theoretical models explored have become partially disconnected from the specific policy implementation, and early assessments may not fully capture the nuanced economic and regulatory dynamics now central to discussions around the EU CBAM. One predominant issue in these early models was the broad sectoral coverage (Kuusi et al., 2020). Researchers typically hypothesised a wide-ranging application across multiple industries, which may have overestimated the mechanism's potential to mitigate carbon leakage and its overall impacts. The actual coverage of the EU CBAM was restricted to a narrow portion of upstream sectors (Tsang et al., 2021). Secondly, earlier studies often incorporated weaker carbon pricing as many did not anticipate the rapid escalation in ETS prices, significantly altering the baseline for assessing competitiveness impacts (Kuik and Hofkes, 2010, Sitarz et al., 2024). Furthermore, it should be taken into consideration that free allowances will remain partially allocated over an extended period, offering EU industries more time to adjust to cleaner production processes and buffering the immediate disruptions anticipated from the EU CBAM.

More recent studies have offered a refined view of the CBAM expected economic and sectoral impacts. The EU impact assessment predicts a modest contraction of the EU's GDP with reductions in imports, to a degree that depends on the specific policy design analysed (European Commission, 2021). Deeper insights into differential impacts across sectors and regions unveil that while CBAM may mitigate some competitive losses, its effects will vary widely, suggesting that global trade dynamics could favour nations with greener production technologies (Chateau et al., 2023) and, in turn, disadvantage exports from carbon-intensive economies. Since the latter tend to be the least-developed countries which may heavily depend on trade with the EU, many have raised concerns over CBAM's distributional repercussions (UNCTAD, 2021; Park et al., 2023; ACF, 2023).

Recent literature has increasingly applied computational general equilibrium (CGE) models to offer nuanced predictions about CBAM long-term outcomes since they portray complex interdependencies between economic sectors and global trade under new regulatory scenarios. For instance, analysis has indicated potential declines in

iron and steel exports from major producers like China, Russia, and Brazil to the EU by 2030 (Xiaobei et al., 2022). Other relevant trading partners such as India, Ukraine and Egypt are also set to suffer from relatively large export losses. Besides trade impacts, CGE modelling has also unveiled the employment implications of the CBAM and their repercussions in terms of political acceptability and regional inequalities across EU member states (Perdana and Vielle, 2024).

This paper aims to contribute to this strand of literature by (i) refining the sectoral coverage; (ii) integrating the specific scope and sequencing of the policy measures; (iii) contemplating a scenario where China and India charge explicit carbon prices and are granted. In fact, the analyses done so far have not yet sufficiently explored the interaction of CBAM and the offsetting of carbon price differentials. Finally, this analysis aims to contribute to the discussion on how these dynamics could foster broader international cooperation on carbon pricing and, eventually, lead to a more globally coordinated approach to emissions reduction.

4.3. Methodology

4.3.1. The FIDELIO model

We employ the FIDELIO model to estimate the impact of EU CBAM and Chinese and Indian carbon control policies. FIDELIO is a global macroeconomic multi-sectoral multi-regional model built on the FIGARO input-output (IO) database and designed to analyse interactions across countries and sectors. The model derives bilateral trade flows based on import-export relationships, with import amount and distribution determined by Armington elasticities. To satisfy the domestic and foreign demand, firms choose the optimal combination of materials, energy services, capital and labour, determined through a nested CES production function. Firms' production generates income that is distributed to the different agents. Household income—net of taxes and social security contributions—and endogenous saving rates determine household consumption level. The optimum allocation of household expenditure across commodities is then modelled through an Almost Ideal Demand System model that endogenously determines consumption shares by income quintile. Government revenues—the sum of government operating surplus and taxes on products, production, and household income—are allocated to government interests, capital formation, government consumption, and household transfers, highlighting the role of government in economic stimulation and welfare provision.

To provide a more realistic description of agents' behaviours, some specific characteristics of the model distinguish FIDELIO from more standard CGE models while getting it closer to neo-Keynesian macro-econometric models. One significant departure lies in how the model determines the cost of capital and labour. Unlike CGE models assuming perfect competition and the equivalence between capital cost and

the remuneration of capital, in FIDELIO, the cost of capital is the same across sectors and depends on the average price of the capital stock, the depreciation of capital and interest rates (see Jorgenson, 1963; Romer, 2012). Similarly, while many CGE models assume interest rates equate savings and investments, FIDELIO sets interest rates via a Taylor rule, reflecting the inflation-economic activity trade-off of the Central Bank (Taylor, 1993). Wages do not clear the labour market and depend positively on the expected consumption price and labour productivity, as well as negatively on the unemployment rate. This relation can be identical to the Phillips curve or the Wage Setting curve, depending on the value of the selected parameters (Heyer et al., 2007; Reynès, 2010). FIDELIO also has a distinctive dynamic framework. This is driven partly by exogenous variables like population and technical progress. The endogenous dynamic of the model is defined not only by capital accumulation, as in many Walrasian models, but also by rigidities that prevent agents from adjusting their economic behaviour to the optimum instantaneously. For a full description of the model assumptions, equations and data, see Rocchi et al. (2024).

Within this general modelling framework, CBAM is introduced through a tariff on imports of covered commodities. The ad valorem tariff depends on the direct carbon intensity of the imported goods, the EU carbon price, and the CBAM phase-in percentage. All three factors evolve over time. The resulting prices of the commodities imported to the EU, together with the domestic EU prices and the Armington elasticities, determine each EU country's total import and bilateral trade flows.

Furthermore, we account for other policies such as the gradual phase-out of free allowances under the EU ETS along with explicit carbon pricing in China and India. These measures exert an impact on the cost of energy commodities employed in production processes, thereby influencing both trade patterns and emission levels. In our model, we distinguish between energy services derived from electricity and energy services derived from other energy sources to represent shifts towards electrification due to carbon policies accurately. To model both policy provisions, we incorporate an additional cost to the energy input prices used in the production function. Although cap-and-trade systems and carbon taxes differ in their implementation, our simplified modelling framework represents each economic sector by a single illustrative firm reflecting the average technological efficiency across existing companies. Consequently, for the sake of simplicity, the price established by an ETS can be reasonably approximated by a tax on carbon and not as a market of allowances which needs to match supply and demand. The interaction and drivers behind an ETS are beyond the scope of the analysis which will assume an exogenous trajectory of carbon prices. Appendix A provides a detailed formulation of the methodology implemented.

4.3.2. Data

The bulk of the data used in the FIDELIO model comes from the international supply and use tables of the FIGARO database (2022 release), the data used for the model calibration referring to 2015. FIGARO stands for 'Full International and Global Accounts for Research in IO analysis' and consists of multi-regional IO official statistics regularly compiled by Eurostat. Additional information required for calibrating FIDELIO is taken from Eurostat, OECD, and World Bank. For a full description of all the model data sources and use, see Rocchi et al. (2024). The geographical coverage of the model corresponds to the one available in the FIGARO database, which is 46 regions. Appendix B provides a list of the FIDELIO countries.

Additional data are required for the analysis. First, the CBAM analysis runs into a methodological challenge. The industry granularity of the model differs from the specific products affected by the policy as it aggregates other products not subject to the tariffs. For instance, in the FIDELIO sectoral granularity, cement is grouped under the category of "other non-metallic mineral products" (C23), which also includes manufactures made with glass, a good not covered by CBAM.

To overcome this limitation, we use the additional database FIGARO-E3. This is a highly disaggregated extended inter-country supply, use and IO database consistent with FIGARO. Available for 2015, the database encompasses data for 213 products and 176 industries, with the same geographical coverage as FIGARO (Cazcarro et al., 2024). The database offers disaggregated data on both energy and emissions. Energy accounts cover primary supply and net use, while GHG emissions cover CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, and fluorinated gases from combustion and non-combustion processes.

We use this very detailed database to add three relevant pieces of information to our analysis. First, we estimate the emission intensity of imported commodities and energy inputs used by firms for computing CBAM tariffs and the domestic carbon prices applied. Although the model's sectoral granularity does not perfectly match the CBAM coverage, the emission intensities used pertain to the specific industries addressed by CBAM. Second, we compute weighting factors to adjust policy costs in the model, preventing any overestimation arising from FIDELIO's sectoral granularity. When dealing with the CBAM, the adjustment represents the weight of each product within the FIDELIO commodity imported by any EU country from non-EU countries. Regarding the phasing out of free allowances in the EU ETS and the foreign carbon control policies, the adjustment reflects the weight of each EITE industry within the FIDELIO industry. Finally, we use the FIGARO-E3 database to split the FIDELIO electricity production into multiple industries, each using different power generation technologies. The electricity sector, under a carbon price scheme, is incentivized to transition towards cleaner energy sources by making them relatively more competitive. As renewable energy deployment increases, the carbon intensity of electricity decreases, affecting the carbon policy burden over time. Appendix C provides a list of all industries used for the analysis.

While the data necessary to split the power generation sector by technology is available in the FIGARO-E3 database, we keep the evolution of these technologies in electricity production exogenous to the model. To represent their transition, we use two alternative sources. First, we use the dynamic evolution of the electricity production shares provided by the WITCH model. WITCH is a global dynamic model integrating the interactions between the economy, the technological options, and climate change. From the same model, we take the elasticity between electrical and non-electrical energy services. Alternatively, and as sensitivity analysis, we turn to the IEA's World Energy Outlook, which provides projected electricity shares by source in the main World regions. More in detail we consider the forecasts that assume a stated policy scenario based on the latest policy settings, including energy, climate and related industrial policies (IEA, 2023). In both cases, the ETS carbon price projections used for the FIDELIO simulations—and for the WITCH simulations that provide the transition in power generation—are again taken from the IEA's World Energy Outlook. See Appendix D for further details on the carbon prices used.

4.3.3. Baseline and policy setting

We start our analysis from a baseline scenario, where the exogenous drivers of the model dynamic for each country—population growth and labour productivity growth—are taken from the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) database provided by the International Institute for Applied Systemic Analysis (IIASA). In particular, we refer to the SSP2 framework, defined as the “middle of the road” framework, that assumes that the World follows a path in which social, economic, and technological trends do not shift markedly from historical patterns. Our baseline scenario already includes the EU ETS revised regulation: the EU ETS permits are assumed to be auctioned fully in the electricity sector while in the industrial sectors, free allocation is phased out according to the scheme presented in the ETS revision as in Figure 13 (European Parliament and Council, 2023a). Revenues collected from the elimination of freely allocated ETS allowances are redistributed to the European countries most affected by the policy, contributing to government expenditure as well as household redistribution.

Figure 13: CBAM over time. Phase-out of freely allocated ETS allowances and corresponding CBAM phase-in.

Source: own elaboration based on European Parliament and Council (2023a).

We then deviate from the baseline scenario to analyse several policy scenarios, modelling three distinct policies, either individually or in combination. The first policy is CBAM. Following what was established by the European Parliament and Council (2023a), the sectors covered in the CBAM scenario are iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, and cement. Given the analysis' focus on evaluating the economic impact of the EU's current policy, the CBAM sectoral scope is not expanded over time. Finally, the assumptions regarding the redistribution and expenditure of the additional revenues generated by the CBAM are extended to the ETS.

Second, we model a Chinese carbon price mechanism similar to the EU ETS applied to the EITE industries that lie under the scope of CBAM (iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers and cement). This policy partly reflects the prospect of an expansion in their national ETS to include these commodities. Besides, we assume that the Chinese ETS fully covers electricity generation. As aforementioned, currently allowances in this scheme are issued to operators for free according to intensities and not absolute emissions. A gradual transition to auctioning would alleviate distortions in the allocation process, thereby enhancing the plausibility of qualifying for a CBAM waiver. This policy setting requires the formulation of a hypothetical Chinese carbon price trajectory. Currently, the oversupply of free allowances has created a market with low carbon prices, hovering around 8 EUR per tonne of CO₂ (Yin, 2023). By assuming a gradual auctioning of allowances for both EITE industries and power generation

plants, a carbon price increase is expected. Projections for this scenario are derived from the IEA's World Energy Outlook (IEA, 2023), assuming a rise up to 40 EUR per tonne of CO₂.

The final policy modelled is a carbon price mechanism implemented by India similar to the EU ETS on the EITE industries and on the power generation sector. This partly draws on the evolving carbon pricing landscape in India which was developed following the implementation of the CBAM, suggesting that the EU, alongside the broader international focus on climate change, may have catalysed this progress. When formalising such policy setting, there is no reliable information on a hypothetical Indian carbon price and its evolution over time. Therefore, we use the same carbon prices as China. Sensitivity analyses of the results are tested based on alternative assumptions. The hypothesis regarding the gradual implementation of the policy and the consequent carbon price are consistent with those applied to the Chinese scenario. Table 14 describes the policies implemented in each of the scenarios analysed.

Table 14: Policies implemented in each scenario

Scenario	Policy implemented
Baseline	Full EU ETS (it includes EU ETS allowances phasing out for EITE sectors).
CBAM	Full EU ETS and EU CBAM (the sectors covered in the CBAM scenario are iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, and cement).
Chinese ETS	Full EU ETS and Chinese ETS on CBAM industries (the Chinese ETS on the power sector becomes more stringent, with a higher carbon price up to 40 EUR per tonne of CO ₂).
Chinese ETS + CBAM	Full EU ETS, Chinese ETS and CBAM.
Indian ETS	Full EU ETS and Indian ETS on CBAM and power sectors (with a carbon price up to 40 EUR per tonne of CO ₂).
Indian ETS + CBAM	Full EU ETS, Indian ETS and EU CBAM.
Chinese and Indian ETS	Full EU ETS, Chinese and Indian ETS.
Chinese and Indian ETS + CBAM	Full EU ETS, Chinese and Indian ETS and EU CBAM.

Source: own elaboration.

Besides the baseline and the CBAM scenario, whose comparison is aimed at providing a first assessment of the impact of CBAM, we look at scenarios where China, India, or both implement their carbon pricing policies, together with the EU ETS. These three policy scenarios are implemented with and without CBAM to explore the impact of the

latter on trade flows and the general macroeconomic and environmental impacts of the policies.

4.4. Results

4.4.1. CBAM

An initial analysis focuses on the CBAM policy scenario over a fifteen-year horizon, extending to the year 2040. The results are presented as deviations (percentage variation) from the baseline scenario that includes the full EU ETS.

Figure 14 shows the expected annual CO₂ emissions variation, in 2030 and 2040. The plot shows the total change by region (blue bars) as well as the variation across manufacturing industries. Countries are grouped into seven main regions, with distinctions made between Eastern (EEU), Northern (NWEU), and Southern (SEU) European countries. Industries are classified by energy intensity into high (HEI), medium (MEI), and low energy-intensive (LEI) industries. Industries producing the commodities to which the CBAM applies fall within HEIs.

Figure 14: CBAM environmental impact. CO₂ emissions variation in CBAM scenario with respect to baseline, 2030 and 2040.

Source: own elaboration. Note: European countries are reflected in the grey shaded area, key trading partners in the white area, and aggregated global values in the green area.

In terms of environmental impact, the analysis suggests that CBAM is expected to induce a global, albeit negligible, decrease in CO₂ emissions. Conversely, there is a

slight increase in EU CO₂ emissions, particularly in Eastern Europe. The observed rise in sectoral emissions can be attributed to an upsurge in production activity which, in turn, leads to a commensurate increase in emissions from energy-intensive commodities. This can be interpreted as mitigation of potential leakage that might have occurred if the ETS for EITE sectors had been phased out without the implementation of CBAM.

Turning to the economic implications, Figure 15 illustrates the regional impact on GDP and manufacturing industry output in 2030 and 2040, respectively.

Figure 15: CBAM macroeconomic impact. GDP and output variation in CBAM scenario with respect to baseline, 2030 and 2040.

Source: own elaboration.

Consistent with the EC impact assessment on CBAM (European Commission, 2021), our analysis indicates that the macroeconomic impact of the current policy design is negligible for both EU and non-EU countries. Even if results slightly differ among regions, the size of the GDP variation is always less than 0.5%. The analysis suggests an initially positive, yet getting negative, impact on European economies, particularly in the Eastern regions. Besides the United States' GDP which exhibits a marginally positive trend, variations in other regions appear negative, albeit of negligible magnitude.

Increasing the resolution of the analysis, the points in Figure 15 represent variations in sectoral output, with economic sectors grouped on the basis of their energy intensity.

Similarly, the impact on European economies remains modest, although somehow more pronounced. Notably, this is attributed primarily to an increase in production from HEIs, which now face less stringent competition in the international arena. The positive impact for HEIs production reaches around 1.5% in 2030 and 2% in 2040. These results are still at a relatively high level of aggregation, both in terms of countries and sectors. For instance, when examining specific EU countries where CBAM industries constitute a significant share of total production, the output variation for HEIs could increase by up to 3% in Belgium, the Czech Republic, and Slovenia, and by 6% in Bulgaria. In contrast, Europe experiences a slight decline in other sectors, offsetting the positive impact in HEIs, resulting in a minor economic contraction in 2040. The variation in the output of the energy intensive sectors is what determines the variation in the GDP also for non-EU countries, with generally less pronounced variations.

We now present results focusing on international trade flows. Figure 16 illustrates the change in trade of manufactured commodities, shown as deviations from the baseline scenario. These commodities are classified according to the energy intensity of the sectors producing them. In addition to disaggregating trade into product groups, the graph displays bilateral trade flows. Each column represents the trading partner from which a region imports, while each row indicates the trading partner to which a region exports. The last row and the last column show the total imports and total exports of each region, respectively.

Figure 16: CBAM trade impact. Bilateral trade flows variation of manufacturing commodities, CBAM scenario.

Source: own elaboration.

As expected, given that the CBAM is an EU policy that directly impacts trade flows, the variations in international trade are greater than those in sectoral output, and the bilateral trade flows exhibiting the greatest variations are those that involve the EU. More in detail, considering the goods that fall under the CBAM regime (HEI), the implementation of the CBAM induces a partial substitution of imports from India, China, Russia, and the ROW with products from the USA. Due to their lower environmental impact, these US products become more competitive after the imposition of the European tariff. The CBAM also increases intra-EU trade, rebalancing competitiveness between goods produced in Europe (and subject to the European ETS) and imported goods. This is what drives total EU imports of HEI commodities up, intra-EU trade being counted within the total imports. Excluding intra-EU trade, EU imports of HEI commodities are expected to decrease by about 7%. Interestingly, there is a slight decrease in EU exports to non-EU countries. For high energy-intensive commodities, this is driven, at least in part, by increased intra-EU trade. Another determinant, even for non-HEI goods, could be the increased price of CBAM commodities and the resulting repercussions on the production chains of other goods that use CBAM commodities as inputs.

4.4.2. Alternative policy scenarios

To analyse the results of the alternative policy settings, we propose two different approaches. First, considering that CBAM is driven primarily by environmental objectives, we aim to evaluate the environmental and macroeconomic impacts of the alternative policies described before. To evaluate the environmental and macroeconomic impacts of the emission control policies that China and India are considering, we compare changes in GDP and CO₂ emissions against the baseline scenario where neither country increases its emission control ambitions and the EU is not enforcing any boarder adjustment mechanism but only the evolution of the EU ETS. Figure 17 shows the variation of CO₂ emissions and variation of real GDP for Europe, China, India, and the rest of the World, in 2040, under the alternative policy scenarios analysed.

Figure 17: Macroscale impacts of alternative scenarios. CO₂ and real GDP variation in 2040 for 4 macro-regions, alternative policy scenarios.

Source: own elaboration.

As expected, the magnitude of the environmental and economic impacts for countries implementing emission control policies differs significantly from the impacts of implementing the CBAM shown in Figure 14. Enacting these carbon control policies, China could achieve a total CO₂ emission reduction of about 26% by 2040. India could experience a similar reduction compared to a baseline scenario with the simulated carbon policy. However, global CO₂ emissions (forth inset in Figure 17) are more affected by Chinese policies, as China accounts for around 30% of global emissions, while India accounts for only 7%. The global variation of CO₂ emissions accounts also for the CO₂ emission increase experienced by other regions such as the EU. As Chinese and Indian products become more expensive and less competitive when national policies are enacted, EU own production and CO₂ increase slightly compared to the reference scenario without Chinese and Indian stricter carbon policies.

Reducing emissions entails an economic cost in terms of GDP losses. As expected, increasing production costs, climate policies have overall a negative effect on GDP.

The two countries show similar GDP impact, around 2%, when they solely act their own policy.

It is worth noticing how the two countries, either China or India, react to emission control policies implemented by the other country unilaterally. When only India takes the lead in applying stringent carbon pricing policies, the impact on the Chinese economy is minimal. The analysis shows a slight, but insignificant, increase in CO₂ emissions and a negligible decrease in GDP. When China enforces more stringent carbon policies and India doesn't follow suit, the Indian economy experiences more significant effects. On the one hand, India gains a pronounced competitive advantage in energy-intensive commodities, resulting in more energy-intensive production and increased emissions around 2.5%. On the other hand, the analysis also shows a negative impact on sectors that are less energy intensive but more value added intensive. The overall GDP variation is negative in sign because these energy-intensive commodities contribute less to GDP than the other sectors whose production decreases. However, the GDP variation on the Indian economy resulting from China undertaking climate action is negligible. When both countries move together, climate policy costs in terms of GDP loss and emission reductions are lower than when the policy is enacted unilaterally. This is more pronounced for India, because of the asymmetric response in the two economies we just highlighted.

We now address the question of what is the impact of CBAM in a context where China and India undertake climate action. Figure 18 shows the change in EU imports import of energy-intensive commodities from China (left inset) and India (right inset) due to CBAM under the four policy scenarios: namely when neither, China, India or both undertake additional carbon policies. As previously described, the carbon prices for China and India in our simulation are lower than the EU carbon price.

Figure 18: CBAM under alternative scenarios. CBAM impact on European import of energy intensive commodities from China and India considering different national decarbonization efforts in the benchmark scenario.

Source: own elaboration

It is important to note that Figure 8 illustrates the impact of the CBAM across different policy scenarios, using these scenarios as benchmarks for analysis and subsequently introducing the CBAM into each. The figure does not assess the direct impact of national emission control policies on trade but rather demonstrates how the effects of the CBAM are shaped by the presence of such domestic policies. The introduction of CBAM in almost all the scenarios analysed reduces exports to the EU, whether countries enforce stricter carbon control policies or not. The black line in Figure 18 represents the case analysed previously, when looking at CBAM without taking into account additional decarbonization efforts from other regions. An increase in Chinese and Indian own decarbonization efforts significantly reduces the negative impact of CBAM on energy-intensive commodities exported to the EU. This outcome is driven by the combined effect of a lower CBAM tariff applied if a country implements more stringent emission control policies and by the reduction in emission intensity of these goods resulting from domestic carbon control measures. When India adopts a carbon pricing mechanism, the implementation of the CBAM, compared to a scenario without CBAM, leads to an increase in Indian exports to the EU. The reduction in emissions driven by India's domestic policy, combined with the lowering of European tariffs, enhances India's comparative advantage.

The only scenario where EU imports from China or India decrease more than when neither country adopts a national carbon policy as a result from CBAM is when the other country alone implements climate mitigation measures. CBAM reduces the competitive advantage that either country would gain from the other's unilateral

carbon pricing. The impact has different scales, highlighting the asymmetric effects of each country's emission reduction policies on the other, due to their different market sizes and trade flows with the EU.

4.5. Conclusions

This paper examines the carbon border adjustment the EU started to roll out in 2023, a policy which has elicited substantial debates in both academic and political spheres. The primary objective is to assess the environmental and macroeconomic effects of the CBAM in its current form and scope.

In terms of environmental impact, our ex-ante policy analysis confirms that, in its current design, the policy meets its primary objective and is expected to induce a global decrease in CO₂ emissions. The expected reduction in emissions, however, remains quite small. The result suggests that the environmental effectiveness of the analysed carbon border adjustment may be sought more in its indirect impacts. First, the carbon border adjustment may have played a crucial role in making the phase-out of the ETS in energy-intensive sectors more politically acceptable to EU Member States. Second, its effectiveness may stem from its ability to provoke responses from the European Union's trading partners.

However, our results show a small increase in emissions, particularly in Eastern Europe, due to the increased European demand of energy-intensive commodities. On the one hand, this should be adequately interpreted, considering that CBAM can mitigate the negative implications of free allowances phase out to energy intensive firms in Eastern Europe. On the other hand, this result highlights the importance of planning and implementing adequate policies for the decarbonisation of industrial production in a timely manner. The revision of the ETS certainly goes in this direction, as does the EU's decades-long experience in properly set the carbon market to obtain an effective carbon price.

In terms of macroeconomic impacts, our analysis confirms that the current CBAM policy design has negligible implications (impacts on GDP that is always lower than 0.5%) for both EU and non-EU countries. Hence, concerns about overall economic implications cannot by itself explain or justify the extensive reactions CBAM has provoked. However, these macro-level results should not dismiss the significant sector-specific effects of the policy. Our analysis demonstrates that CBAM exerts a pronounced impact on the production and trade of commodities within highly energy-intensive sectors. Sector specific compensatory measures should be accordingly planned.

In terms of trade flows, if foreign nations do not make concerted efforts to implement policies that foster the decarbonisation of their industrial processes, CBAM induces a

partial substitution of imports from countries whose production is more emission-intensive, such as India, China, or Russia, with products from countries with cleaner technologies, such as the USA and the EU. Consequently, this analysis underscores the necessity of investigating the micro-level impacts on specific sectors and regions, such as downstream products and least-developed countries, as well as issues of political economy and industrial strategy, in Europe as in other countries. These are questions that, while beyond the scope of this paper, appear highly relevant for future research.

These results and the numerous political reactions to CBAM suggest that a comprehensive evaluation of the EU policy under analysis should consider the potential dynamic implications that this tool entails. For this reason, the second proposal of this paper is to analyse a broader context of carbon pricing policies by focusing on two key global players, China and India.

From this perspective, the analysis highlights that national emission control policies exhibit environmental and economic impacts that are not comparable to those induced by the sole introduction of trade measures. Therefore, it may be naive to attribute this renewed impetus in adopting carbon pricing solely to comply with the CBAM policy. Instead, these may be driven by a series of factors. The obvious motive lies in the increasing need and willingness to abate emissions in a cost-effective and fiscally sustainable manner.

Nevertheless, it should be recognised that the EU, by pursuing the CBAM and enlarging the reach of its own ETS, is moving the needle on the global development of compliance carbon market frameworks by setting a precedent on how to deal with carbon leakage, strengthening the credibility of its own price signals while elevating the role of emission measurement and reporting as a central pillar of future climate policy. While CBAM cannot be considered the only or main driver of more stringent emission control policies implemented by trading partners, our analysis indicates that if we look at carbon tariffs within a framework of stringent international carbon control policies, impacts on international trade flows are mitigated. For this scenario to materialise, far-reaching diplomatic efforts will be crucial in fostering international cooperation and attenuating trade contentions. Actively supporting carbon pricing adoption via technical assistance can steer foreign countries towards climate-compatible trajectories. This recommendation becomes particularly relevant if additional countries follow suit and adopt their own border adjustments, further strengthening the economic appeal of adopting carbon pricing instruments.

Another insightful takeaway can be drawn from the observed interaction between carbon pricing policies from different countries: CBAM strategically connects countries for which trade with the EU is important. In the proposed case study, CBAM attenuates the significant competitive advantage India could gain when China

implements more stringent carbon policies, creating to a certain extent incentives for India to undertake some form of climate policy once China moves ahead. Besides, our findings highlight that the economic impact of environmental policies can be asymmetrical between trading partners. This disparity is partly due to the differences in market size, composition and relevance for the EU. Carbon border adjustments may start to play a role in aligning carbon policies between countries, incorporating a stronger strategic dimension to government actions. Such dynamics are set to heavily influence countries with export-driven economies reliant on the production of carbon-intensive commodities. Further studies could delve deeper into when nations wary of carbon pricing begin to lose their comparative advantages, potentially via models that capture both technical and structural changes.

Additional sensitivity analysis could assess to what extent results vary under alternative price scenarios. As sectorial scope enlarges and markets and technologies evolve, carbon prices may produce changes ridden with uncertainty. Economic and trade outcomes may prove to be highly dependent on price fluctuations, as well as by how governments allocate the collected revenues. Different redistributive schemes could channel support towards climate-related initiatives, energy-intensive industries, or households, either domestically or internationally through development aid.

In conclusion, while the EU CBAM undoubtedly raises several valid concerns—such as counterproductive trade reshuffling, adverse impacts on developing economies, reporting loopholes and administrative burdens, protectionist tendencies, and the risk of multilateral trade disputes—some of these fears may have been somewhat overstated. The narrative has largely focused on CBAM’s flaws and how it will upend trade relations, often overlooking the policy’s design and its dynamic nature. Notably, a gradual implementation and an initially limited scope are important details that may prove to mitigate some of these concerns. Moreover, such policies are driving significant research efforts and refocusing attention on carbon pricing as a cornerstone of climate action. Trade measures addressing competitiveness issues should be viewed as one component of the broader climate policy framework, designed to advance carbon pricing and industrial decarbonization.

4.6. References

ACF, 2023. Implications for African countries of a carbon border adjustment mechanism in the EU. African Climate Foundation and the London School Of Economics and Political Science Report.
<https://africanclimatefoundation.org/research-article/implications-for-african-countries-of-a-carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism-in-the-eu/>.

Beaufils, T., Ward, H., Jakob, M. et al., 2023. Assessing different European Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism implementations and their impact on trade

- partners. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 4, 131. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-00788-4>.
- Bellora, C., Fontagné, L., 2023. EU in search of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism. *Energ. Econ.*, 123, 106673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2023.106673>.
- Böhringer, C., Carbone, J.C., Rutherford, T.F., 2018. Embodied carbon tariffs. *Scand. J. Econ.*, 120, 183–210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjoe.12211>.
- Böhringer, C., Fischer, C., Rosendahl, K.E., 2010. The global effects of subglobal climate policies. *The B.E. J.Econ. Anal. Pol.*, 10, 2, 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.2202/1935-1682.2583>.
- Böhringer, C., Fischer, C., Rosendahl, K.E., Rutherford, T.F., 2022. Potential impacts and challenges of border carbon adjustments. *Nat. Clim. Change*, 12, 22–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01250-z>.
- Cao, J., Dai, H.C., Li, S.T., Guo, C.Y., Ho, M., Cai, W.J., He, J.W., Huang, H., Li, J.F., Liu, Y., Qian, H.Q., Wang, C., Wu, L.B., Zhang, X.L., 2021. The general equilibrium impacts of carbon tax policy in China: A multi-model comparison. *Energy Econ*, 99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105284>
- Cazcarro, I., Usubiaga-Liaño, A., Román, M.V., Piñero, P., Dietzenbacher, E., Rueda-Cantuche, J.M., Arto, I., 2024. Classifications. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC). <http://data.europa.eu/89h/22eb94b9-79be-42e5-8c4b-ac441a543cfa>.
- Chateau, J., Miho, A., Borowiecki, M., 2023. Economic effects of the EU's 'Fit for 55' climate mitigation policies: A computable general equilibrium analysis. OECD Economics Department Working Papers, 1775, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/f1a8cfa2-en>.
- Clora, F., Yu, W., Corong, E., 2023. Alternative carbon border adjustment mechanisms in the European Union and international responses: Aggregate and within-coalition results. *Energ. Policy*, 174, 113454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113454>.
- Cosbey, A., Droege, S., Fischer, C., Reinaud, J., Stephenson, J., Weischer, L., Wooders, P., 2012. A guide for the concerned: Guidance on the elaboration and implementation of Border Carbon Adjustment. *Entwined Policy Report*, 03. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2178312>.
- Crippa, M., Guizzardi, D., Pagani, F., Banja, M., Muntean, M., Schaaf E., Becker, W., Monforti-Ferrario, F., Quadrelli, R., Risquez Martin, A., Taghavi-Moharamli, P., Köykkä, J., Grassi, G., Rossi, S., Brandao De Melo, J., Oom, D., Branco, A., San-

- Miguel, J., Vignati, E., 2023. GHG emissions of all world countries. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, JRC134504. <https://doi.org/10.2760/953322>.
- Delbeke, J., 2024. How the EU can support carbon pricing at global level. EUI, STG, Policy Paper, 2024/12. <https://doi.org/10.2870/167326>.
- Delbeke, J., Dombrowicki, P., Vis, P., 2021. Key issues for the coming trade and climate debate. EUI STG policy papers. STG Policy Briefs, 2021/12. <https://doi.org/10.2870/163281>.
- Delbeke, J., Vis, P., 2023. How CBAM can become a steppingstone towards carbon pricing globally. EUI, STG, Policy Brief, 2023/06. <https://doi.org/10.2870/603414>.
- European Commission, 2021. Commission Staff Working Document Impact Assessment Report Accompanying The Document Proposal For A Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council Establishing a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism. Brussels, SWD(2021), 643 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021SC0643>.
- European Parliament and Council, 2023a. Regulation (eu) 2023/956 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 establishing a carbon border adjustment mechanism. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.L_.2023.130.01.0052.01.ENG&%3Btoc=OJ%3AL%3A2023%3A130%3ATOC.
- European Parliament and Council, 2023b. Directive (EU) 2023/959 Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 10 May 2023 amending Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and Decision (EU) 2015/1814 concerning the establishment and operation of a market stability reserve for the Union greenhouse gas emission trading system. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/959/oj>.
- Espa, I., Francois, J., van Asselt, H., 2022. The EU proposal for a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM): An analysis under WTO and climate change law. WTI Working Paper No. 06/2022. <https://www.wti.org/research/publications/1375/the-eu-proposal-for-a-carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism-cbam-an-analysis-under-wto-and-climate-change-law/>.
- Fredriksson, G., Zachmann, G., 2021. Assessing the distributional effects of the European Green Deal. EconPol Forum, CESifo GmbH. <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/250934>.

- Heyer, E., Reynès, F., and Sterdyniak, H., 2007. Structural and reduced approaches of the equilibrium rate of unemployment, a comparison between France and the United States. *Econ. Model.*, 24, 1, 42–65.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2006.06.005>.
- ICAP, 2024. Emissions Trading worldwide: Status report 2024. Berlin: International Carbon Action Partnership.
https://icapcarbonaction.com/system/files/document/240416_report_final.pdf.
- IEA, 2023. World energy outlook 2023. Paris. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 4.0.
<https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2023>.
- IETA, 2024. The international reaction to the EU carbon border adjustment mechanism. https://ieta.b-cdn.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/IETA_INTL-REACTION-TO-CBAM-REPORT.pdf
- Jorgenson, D. W., 1963. Capital theory and investment behavior. *Am. Econ. Rev.*, 53, 2, 247–259.
- Kolev, G., 2021. Carbon Border Adjustment and other trade policy approaches for climate protection. *Intereconomics*, ISSN 1613-964X, Springer, Heidelberg, 56, 6, 310–316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10272-021-1007-4>.
- Kuik, O., Hofkes, M., 2010. Border adjustment for European emissions trading: Competitiveness and carbon leakage. *Energ. Policy*, 38, 4, 1741–1748.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.11.048>.
- Kuusi, T., Björklund, M., Kaitila, V., Kokko, K., Lehmus, M., Mehling, M., Oikarinen, T., Pohjola, J., Soimakallio, S., Wang, M., 2020. Carbon border adjustment mechanisms and their economic impact on Finland and the EU. *Publications of the Government's analysis, assessment and research activities*, 2020:48.
<http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-287-922-6>.
- Lanzi, E., Chateau, J., Dellink, R., 2012. Alternative approaches for levelling carbon prices in a world with fragmented carbon markets. *Energ. Econ.*, 34, 2, S240–S250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2012.08.016>.
- Magacho, G., Espagne, E., Godin, A., 2024. Impacts of the CBAM on EU trade partners: Consequences for developing countries. *Clim. Policy*, 24, 2, 243–259.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2023.2200758>.
- Marcu, A., Mehling, M., Cosbey, A., 2021. Border carbon adjustments in the EU: sectoral deep dive. ERCST European Roundtable on Climate Change and Sustainable Transition. <https://ercst.org/border-carbon-adjustments-in-the-eu-sectoral-deep-dive/>.

- Marcu, A., Mehling, M., Cosbey, A., Svensson, S., 2024. Review of Carbon leakage risks of CBAM export goods. ERCST European Roundtable on Climate Change and Sustainable Transition. <https://ercst.org/review-of-carbon-leakage-risks-of-cbam-export-goods/>.
- Mehling, M. A., van Asselt, H., Das, K., Droege, S., Verkuil, C., 2019. Designing border carbon adjustments for enhanced climate action. *Am. J. Int. Law*, 113, 3, 433–481. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ajil.2019.22>.
- Moss, R., Edmonds, J., Hibbard, K., Manning, M.R., Rose, S.K., van Vuuren, D.P., Carter, T.R., Emori, S., Kainuma, M., Kram, T., Meehl, G.A., Mitchell, J.F.B., Nakicenovic, N., Riahi, K., Smith, S.J., Stouffer, R.J., Thomson, A.M., Weyant, J.P., Wilbanks, T.J., 2010. The next generation of scenarios for climate change research and assessment. *Nature*, 463, 747–756. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08823>.
- Overland, I., Sabyrbekov, R., 2022. Know your opponent: Which countries might fight the European Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism? *Energ. Policy*, 169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113175>.
- Park, C.Y., Yamamoto, Y., Doong, M.A.L., 2023. European Union Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism: Economic impact and implications for Asia. ADB Briefs, 267. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/928466/adb-brief-276-eu-carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism.pdf>.
- Perdana, S., Vielle, M., 2024. Industrial European regions at risk within the Fit for 55: How far implementing CBAM can mitigate? *Renew. Sust. Energ. Trans.*, 6, 100088. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2024.100088>.
- Reynès, F., 2010. The Phillips curve as a more general model than the wage setting curve. OFCE Working paper 2010-28. <http://www.ofce.sciences-po.fr/pdf/dtravail/WP2010-28.pdf>.
- Riahi, K., van Vuuren, D.P., Kriegler, E., Edmonds, J., O'Neill, B.C., Fujimori, S., Bauer, N., Calvin, K., Dellink, R., Fricko, O., Lutz, W., Popp, A., Cuaresma, J.C., Samir KC, Leimbach, M., Jiang, L., Kram, T., Rao, S., Emmerling, J., Ebi, K., Hasegawa, T., Havlik, P., Humpenöder, F., Aleluia Da Silva, L., Smith, S., Stehfest, E., Bosetti, V., Eom, J., Gernaat, D., Masui, T., Rogelj, J., Strefler, J., Drouet, L., Krey, V., Luderer, G., Harmsen, M., Takahashi, K., Baumstark, L., Doelman, J.C., Kainuma, M., Klimont, Z., Marangoni, G., Lotze-Campen, H., Obersteiner, M., Tabeau, A., Tavoni, M., 2017. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: An overview. *Global Environ. Chang.*, 42, 153–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.05.009>.

- Rocchi, P., Reynès, F., Hu, J., Pedauga, L., Cai, M., Boonman, H., Rueda Cantuche, J.M. (2024). FIDELIO 4 manual: Equations and data sources, JRC Technical Report forthcoming, Luxembourg: European Commission.
- Romer, D., 2012. Advanced macroeconomics. New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
- Sitarz, J., Pahle, M., Osorio, S., Luderer, G., Pietzcker, R., 2024. EU carbon prices signal high policy credibility and farsighted actors, *Nature Energy*, 9, 691–702. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-024-01505-x>.
- Sun, X., Mi, Z., Cheng L., Coffman, D., Liu, Y., 2024. The carbon border adjustment mechanism is inefficient in addressing carbon leakage and results in unfair welfare losses. *Fund. Research*, 4, 3, 660–670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fmre.2023.02.026>.
- Taylor, J. B., 1993. Discretion versus policy rules in practice. *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy*, 39, 195–214. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2231\(93\)90009-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2231(93)90009-L).
- Tsang, B., Vangenechten, D., Schäpe, B., Assous, A., Burns, T., 2021. A storm in a teacup impacts and geopolitical risks of the European carbon border adjustment mechanism. E3G & Sanbag Report. <https://www.e3g.org/publications/a-storm-in-a-teacup/>.
- UN Comtrade Database, 2024. Trade data statistics. <https://comtradeplus.un.org/> (accessed 24 July 2024).
- UNCTAD, 2021. A European Union Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism: Implications for developing countries. UNCTAD Report. <https://unctad.org/publication/european-union-carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism-implications-developing-countries>.
- UNFCCC, 2021a. China's achievements, new goals and new measures for Nationally Determined Contributions. <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/China%E2%80%99s%20Achievements%2C%20New%20Goals%20and%20New%20Measures%20for%20Nationally%20Determined%20Contributions.pdf>.
- UNFCCC, 2021b. India's updated first Nationally Determined Contribution under Paris Agreement. <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-08/India%20Updated%20First%20Nationally%20Determined%20Contrib.pdf>.
- von der Leyen, U., 2019. A Union that strives for more. Political guidelines for the next European Commission 2019-2024. https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-04/political-guidelines-next-commission_en_0.pdf.

- Vidovic D., Marmier, A., Zore, L. and Moya, J., 2023. Greenhouse gas emission intensities of the steel, fertilisers, aluminium and cement industries in the EU and its main trading partners, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/359533>.
- Wang Y., Winchester N., Webster C.J., Nam K.-M., 2020. Impacts of China's Emissions Trading Scheme on the national and Hong Kong economies: A Dynamic computable general equilibrium. *Front. Environ. Sci.*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2020.599231>.
- Weitzel, M., Hübler, M., Peterson, S., 2012. Fair, optimal or detrimental? Environmental vs. strategic use of border carbon adjustment. *Energ. Econ.*, 34, 2, S198–S207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2012.08.023>.
- World Bank, 2024a. State and Trends of Carbon Pricing 2024. Washington, DC: World Bank. License: CC BY 3.0 IGO. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/41544>.
- World Bank, 2024b. Relative CBAM exposure index. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/data/interactive/2023/06/15/relative-cbam-exposure-index#2> (accessed 24 July 2024).
- World Steel Associations, 2024. Annual production steel data. https://worldsteel.org/data/annual-production-steel-data/?ind=P1_crude_steel_total_pub/CHN/IND (accessed 24 July 2024).
- Xiaobei, H., Fan, Z., Jun, M., 2022. The global impact of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism: A quantitative assessment. BU Global Development Policy Center Report. <https://www.bu.edu/gdp/files/2022/03/TF-WP-001-FIN.pdf>.
- Yin, I., 2023. Commodities 2023: China's carbon market to slow in 2023 as energy security, economy take priority. S&P Global Commodity Insights. <https://www.spglobal.com/commodity-insights/en/>

Appendix A Methods and relevant equations

With the introduction of the CBAM provision, the price of the commodity c that the EU country n imports from the exporting country r , $p_{n,r,c}^M$, is defined, at any time t , as:

$p_{n,r,c}^M = p_{r,c}^X \times (1 + t_{n,r,c})$. $p_{r,c}^X$ is the price that the exporting country r charges on the commodity's export c and $t_{n,r,c}$ is the ad valorem tariff arising from implementing CBAM in country n on the commodity c imported from country r . The tariff is related to the carbon intensity of the goods imported and computed as follows: $t_{n,r,c} =$

$p_{CO_2}^{EU} \times \varepsilon_{g,r} \times \alpha^{EU} \times \theta_{n,r,c}$. $p_{CO_2}^{EU}$ is the EU ETS price of CO_2 (EUR/tonne of CO_2) and $\varepsilon_{g,r}$ represents the direct CO_2 intensity of any CBAM commodity (tonne of CO_2 /EUR). The emission intensity is computed as the total CO_2 emissions of the industry producing the commodity c divided by the total output value of that industry and evolves over time.

α_t^{EU} is, at any time t , the CBAM gradual phase-in percentage, that mirrors the EU ETS phasing out as for Figure 13. Finally, $\theta_{n,r,c}$ represents the weight of each CBAM product g within the FIDELIO commodity c that any EU country n imports from the non-EU country r . The granularity of the FIDELIO sectors does not coincide with the narrower scope of the CBAM provision. Nevertheless, we use the additional information available in the Figaro-E3 database to compute the emission intensity of the specific CBAM commodities, and we adjust the computed CBAM cost using the weights of each CBAM commodity within the FIDELIO commodities. These weights are also computed using information from the Figaro-E3 database. In contrast to the standard version of the FIDELIO model, a modification was introduced to better capture the policies under examination. This adjustment distinguishes between energy services derived from electricity consumption (el commodity) and those from other energy sources (nel commodities). The CES production function within the model has been accordingly adapted to accommodate a specified substitution level between the two types of energy commodities. This adjustment enables the model to effectively represent potential shifts towards electrification resulting from energy or carbon policies. The additional cost resulting from the phasing out of free EU ETS allowances for EITE industries $t_{n,i}^{nel}$ enters into the firm's cost minimization problem in determining the demand for energy commodities, $nel_{n,i}$ as follows: $nel_{n,i} =$

$\alpha_{n,i}^{nel} \times \left(\left(p_{n,i}^{nel} \times (1 + t_{n,i}^{nel}) \right) / p_{n,i}^e \right)^{-\sigma_e} \times E_{n,i}$. $\alpha_{n,i}^{nel}$ is the base year calibration of the share of nel, $p_{n,i}^{nel}$ is the weighted average price of nel commodities, σ_e is the elasticity of substitution between nel commodities and electricity, while $E_{n,i}$ is the total demand of energy commodities. $p_{n,i}^e$ represents the price of energy commodities, and is derived as follows: $p_{n,i}^e = \left(\alpha_{n,i}^{el} \times (p_{n,i}^{el})^{1-\sigma_e} + \alpha_{n,i}^{nel} \times$

$(p_{n,i}^{nel} \times (1 + t_{n,i}^{nel}))^{1-\sigma_e} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma_e}}$. $\alpha_{n,i}^{el}$ the base year share of electricity and $p_{n,i}^{el}$ its price. In this case, the cost added to the price of the energy commodities used by each

industry is defined as: $t_{n,i}^{nel} = p_{CO_2}^{EU} \times \epsilon_{s,n}^{nel} \times \alpha^{EU} \times \vartheta_{n,i}$. $\epsilon_{s,n}^{nel}$ represents the CO₂ intensity of the energy commodities used by the industry s (tonne of CO₂/EUR). $\vartheta_{n,i}$ represents the weight of each EITE industry s within the FIDELIO industry i of country n .

Appendix B FIDELIO countries, abbreviations and grouping for results visualisation

	Countries	Abbreviation	Grouping
European Countries	Austria	AUT	NWEU
	Belgium	BEL	NWEU
	Bulgaria	BGR	EEU
	Croatia	HRV	EEU
	Cyprus	CYP	SEU
	Czechia	CZE	EEU
	Denmark	DNK	NWEU
	Estonia	EST	EEU
	Finland	FIN	NWEU
	France	FRA	NWEU
	Germany	DEU	NWEU
	Greece	GRC	SEU
	Hungary	HUN	EEU
	Ireland	IRL	NWEU
	Italy	ITA	SEU
	Latvia	LVA	EEU
	Lithuania	LTU	EEU
	Luxembourg	LUX	NWEU
	Malta	MLT	SEU
	Netherlands	NLD	NWEU
	Poland	POL	EEU
	Portugal	PRT	SEU
	Romania	ROU	EEU
	Slovakia	SVK	EEU
	Slovenia	SVN	EEU
	Spain	ESP	SEU
	Sweden	SWE	NWEU
Non-European countries	Argentina	ARG	
	Australia	AUS	
	Brazil	BRA	
	Canada	CAN	
	China	CHN	
	Indonesia	IDN	
	India	IND	
	Japan	JPN	
	Korea	KOR	
	Mexico	MEX	
	Norway	NOR	
	Russia	RUS	
	Saudi Arabia	SAU	
	South Africa	ZAF	
Taiwan	TWN		
Turkey	TUR		

	United Kingdom	GBR	
	United States	USA	
	Rest of the world	ZROW	

Source: Own elaboration

Appendix C List of NACE Rev. 2 industries in FIDELIO

NACE	Industry description
A01	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities
A02	Forestry and logging
A03	Fishing and aquaculture
B	Mining and quarrying
C10T12	Manufacture of food products, beverages and tobacco products
C13T15	Manufacture of textiles, wearing apparel and leather products
C16	Manufacture of wood and products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials
C17	Manufacture of paper and paper products
C18	Printing and reproduction of recorded media
C19	Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products
C20	Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products
C21	Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations
C22	Manufacture of rubber and plastic products
C23	Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products
C24	Manufacture of basic metals
C25	Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
C26	Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products
C27	Manufacture of electrical equipment
C28	Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.
C29	Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers
C30	Manufacture of other transport equipment
C31_32	Manufacture of furniture; other manufacturing
C33	Repair and installation of machinery and equipment
D3511_A	Production of electricity by coal
D3511_B	Production of electricity by gas
D3511_C	Production of electricity by nuclear
D3511_D	Production of electricity by hydro
D3511_E	Production of electricity by wind
D3511_F	Production of electricity by petroleum and other oil derivatives
D3511_G	Production of electricity by biomass and waste
D3511_H	Production of electricity by solar photovoltaic
D3511_I	Production of electricity by solar thermal
D3511_J	Production of electricity by tide, wave, ocean
D3511_K	Production of electricity by Geothermal
D3511_L	Production of electricity nec
D3512- D3513	Transmission of electricity, Distribution and trade of electricity
D352- D353	Manufacture of gas, distribution of gaseous fuels through mains, Steam and hot water supply
E36	Water collection, treatment and supply

NACE	Industry description
E37T39	Sewerage; waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery; remediation activities and other w.m.s.
F	Construction
G45	Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles
G46	Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles
G47	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles
H49	Land transport and transport via pipelines
H50	Water transport
H51	Air transport
H52	Warehousing and support activities for transportation
H53	Postal and courier activities
I	Accommodation; food and beverage service activities
J58	Publishing activities
J59_60	Motion picture, video and TV production, sound recording and music publishing act.; and broadcasting activities
J61	Telecommunications
J62_63	Computer programming, consultancy and related activities; information service activities
K64	Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding
K65	Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security
K66	Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities
L68	Real estate activities
M69_70	Legal and accounting activities; activities of head offices; management consultancy activities
M71	Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis
M72	Scientific research and development
M73	Advertising and market research
M74_75	Other professional, scientific and technical activities; veterinary activities
N77	Rental and leasing services
N78	Employment services
N79	Travel agency, tour operator and other reservation services
N80T82	Security and investigation services; services to buildings and landscape; office administrative, office support and other b.s.s
O84	Public administration and defence; compulsory social security
P85	Education
Q86	Human health services
Q87_88	Residential care services; social work services without accommodation
R90T92	Creative, arts, entertainment, library, archive, museum, other cultural services; gambling and betting services
R93	Sporting services and amusement and recreation services
S94	Services furnished by membership organisations
S95	Repair services of computers and personal and household goods
S96	Other personal services
T	Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods and services producing activities of households for own use
U	Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies

Source: Own elaboration

Appendix D Carbon price evolution for the EU, China and India, based on the IEA Stated Policy Scenario. EUR (2022, MER) per tonne of CO₂

Country	2030	2040
EU	110	119
China	26	40
India *	26	40

* No values are available for India in the Stated Policy Scenario. We use the values of China.

Source: Own elaboration from IEA (2023)